

Topological Forwarding for LEO Constellations: A Scope-Specific Routing Policy in a Recursive User-Plane Architecture

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Abstract

Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite networks are becoming increasingly important for global connectivity in Fifth Generation (5G) and next-generation networks, yet traditional Internet Protocol (IP)-based architectures couple per-satellite forwarding state to constellation size and force continuous route recomputation in a topology whose change is the normal operating state. This paper revisits topological forwarding for modern mega-constellations through the lens of the 6G Recursive User Plane Architecture (6G-RUPA) framework, in which routing is a scope-specific policy of a general recursive architecture rather than a fixed network-wide protocol. Each satellite’s logical position in the constellation is encoded directly into its network address, replacing destination-oriented forwarding tables with local neighbor knowledge, and a pivot-weighted distance estimator captures the latitude-dependent physical asymmetry of inter-plane Inter-Satellite Links (ISLs) directly from measured edge weights, generalizing the constellation-specific analytic delay refinement of classical datagram routing to arbitrary measured geometry. We evaluate this scheme with LEO Path (LEOPath), an open-source simulator, across four commercial constellation designs and two ISL regimes, against link-state and explicit-path routing families. In the regular Ring/+Grid models evaluated, the proposed scheme reduces per-satellite forwarding state from constellation scale (351–1 584 entries) to local degree (2–5 entries), lowers satellite-local routing-table updates by roughly two orders of

magnitude relative to link-state routing, and preserves shortest-path quality within numerical precision; the reduced state also suggests, though we do not measure, lower forwarding-lookup energy. These results support the broader architectural claim that scope-tailored addressing and routing policies allow a single user-plane architecture to span terrestrial and non-terrestrial segments.

Keywords: Routing, LEO satellites, 6G-RUPA, Satellite networks, Topological routing, Network scalability, Network architecture

1. Introduction

With the rapid evolution of wireless communication toward 5G and beyond, Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs), and in particular LEO satellite networks, have emerged as vital enablers of global connectivity. The advent of LEO satellite mega-constellations, driven by private-sector projects like SpaceX’s Starlink, Amazon’s Project Kuiper, and Telesat Lightspeed, is expected to redefine global communications. By deploying thousands of satellites into a dense orbital mesh at altitudes ranging from 300 km and 1,500 km, these networks aim to deliver a ubiquitous, high-speed, and low-latency Internet access [1, 2]. This ambitious goal promises to bridge the digital divide for unserved and underserved communities worldwide, extending communication services to remote geographical areas and supporting the growing demand for a fully connected world. The scale of these networks is unprecedented, with plans for tens of thousands of satellites to form a cohesive global infrastructure.

However, the implementation of LEO satellite networks faces several significant challenges that stem from a fundamental architectural mismatch with legacy terrestrial networking. The core protocols of the internet, namely the IP suite, rely on two key assumptions about node topology and addressing that are fundamentally violated in LEO environments. As per these assumptions, IP addresses serve dual roles as both identifiers (node names) and locators (topological positions), but in LEO networks, a satellite’s topological position changes constantly, given that LEO satellites orbit at speeds of approximately 28,000 km/h [3].

Such high velocities experienced by satellites result in a continuously evolving network topology, a challenge that traditional terrestrial protocols were not designed to handle. This paper argues that the primary challenge

for LEO networks is not technological but architectural: the assumptions about network identity, addressing, and routing for *static* topologies underpinning the established internet protocol suite are inherently incompatible with highly dynamic satellite networks. Consequently, overcoming this mismatch calls for a fundamental rethinking of network design for satellite-based systems.

An important step toward addressing these architectural challenges is a deeper examination of how routing protocols perform in highly dynamic satellite networks. Traditional destination-based routing approaches, and especially link-state protocols such as Open Shortest Path First (OSPF), face serious scalability challenges in LEO constellations. In a link-state system, each satellite must maintain a routing entry for every other node in the constellation to compute shortest-path routes. For a network of N satellites, this results in forwarding tables of size $O(N)$, which becomes unmanageable as constellations scale to thousands or even tens of thousands of nodes. Moreover, link-state routing adds the further burden of continuous topology dissemination and recomputation in a constantly changing LEO environment.

These scalability obstacles also interact with stringent on-board energy limits. Satellites are power-limited systems, and high-speed destination-based forwarding commonly relies on associative lookup structures such as Ternary Content-Addressable Memory (TCAM), whose power consumption grows with the number of stored entries [4, 5]. To the extent that on-board routers adopt such structures, large forwarding tables translate into additional power draw during eclipse-period battery operation. We treat this energy coupling as a secondary motivation, however: the primary, directly measurable costs addressed in this paper are forwarding state and the satellite-local burden of maintaining it.

To address these fundamental limitations, this paper proposes a novel approach for satellite addressing and routing optimized for the dynamic, non-static nature of LEO constellations. We advocate for a shift from traditional IP-based routing towards a topological addressing scheme that encodes a satellite’s logical position within the constellation’s grid directly into its network address. This approach is inspired by the principles emerging from the Sixth Generation (6G) wireless vision, which mandates the native integration of NTN into a single, seamless network fabric [6, 7].

One framework aligned with this vision is 6G-RUPA [8]. We frame it as an *evolutionary generalization* of the mobile-network user plane rather than a clean-slate redesign: it remains backward compatible with existing

5G deployments, while relaxing the assumption that every network segment must run the same fixed protocol and address format end to end. A single architecture thereby generalizes mobile networks across terrestrial and non-terrestrial settings, with each segment defining forwarding and addressing *policies* fitted to its own topology, in layers that are not constrained to one predetermined protocol; these principles trace their lineage to the Recursive InterNetwork Architecture (RINA) [9]. Our previous work motivates this approach for forwarding-state scalability in national-scale terrestrial user planes [10]; the present work focuses on the non-terrestrial segment, where the scalability challenge is more acute because the LEO topology itself is in constant motion.

The idea of forwarding on logical constellation coordinates is not itself new: distributed datagram routing over virtual (*plane, slot*) coordinates was proposed for first-generation LEO systems [11, 12], alongside virtual-topology and virtual-node abstractions that hide orbital motion from the routing layer [13, 14]. Those schemes, however, were conceived as bespoke protocols for isolated constellations. What has changed is the architectural context: modern mega-constellations must integrate with terrestrial mobile networks as one user plane, serve moving ground endpoints whose attachment changes every few minutes, and coexist with traffic-engineering mechanisms. This paper therefore revisits topological forwarding not as a standalone protocol, but as a *scope-specific routing policy* of a general recursive architecture: the same 6G-RUPA user plane that serves terrestrial segments—where topological address aggregation has been shown to keep Generic User Plane Function (GUPF) forwarding state independent of the attached-terminal count [10]—hosts a constellation-backbone scope whose addressing and forwarding policies are tailored to the orbital topology, while identity-locator separation—a principle formalized in RINA [9] and grounded in Saltzer’s foundational work on naming and binding [32]—decouples stable application process identifiers from ephemeral topological locators. A ground station’s application identity persists across satellite attachments; only its topological locator changes as constellation dynamics shift the serving satellite. This decoupling is a core architectural principle of 6G-RUPA [8] and replaces network-wide renumbering with edge-local binding updates.

Concretely, what is new here is neither logical-coordinate forwarding nor identity-locator separation in isolation—both predate this work—but their combination as a *scope-specific policy of a single recursive user plane*, paired with a distance estimator that learns the physical asymmetry of inter-plane

ISLs from *measured* edge weights rather than from a constellation-specific analytic model. The primary contributions of this paper are: (i) the realization of topological addressing and low-state forwarding as a 6G-RUPA backbone-scope policy, including the treatment of ground-station mobility as edge-local destination-locator renumbering; (ii) a pivot-weighted distance estimator that captures the latitude-dependent physical asymmetry of inter-plane ISLs directly from measured edge weights, generalizing the constellation-specific analytic delay refinement of classical datagram routing [11] to arbitrary measured geometry, together with a family-level analytical characterization of the routing alternatives and their expected state, dynamics, and path-quality behavior; and (iii) LEOPath [15], an open-source LEO routing simulator used to validate concrete implementations of those algorithmic families under realistic orbital dynamics in NTN environments. The primary quantitative matrix compares three families: link-state, topological forwarding, and explicit-path. Using LEOPath, we demonstrate orders-of-magnitude forwarding-state reductions compared to link-state routing, together with lower router-local maintenance burden and shortest-path quality within numerical precision in the regular Ring/+Grid models evaluated here.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background information on LEO satellite networks, existing routing approaches, and the architectural principles of 6G-RUPA. Section 3 presents the novel 6G-RUPA addressing scheme and topological routing algorithm, specifically tailored for the dynamic nature of LEO networks. Section 4 then formalizes the routing families and evaluation metrics, and uses LEOPath to validate concrete implementations of those algorithms under dynamic constellation evolution. Section 5 interprets the validated results in a broader architectural context and relates the evaluated families to representative deployed protocol approaches. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

2. Background and Related Work

This section provides the necessary relevant background to situate the proposed approach within the broader LEO networking literature. We first review the physical and operational characteristics that distinguish LEO constellations from terrestrial networks, and then discuss common ISL topology designs along with their implications for routing. Finally, we examine the main architectural approaches for satellite networking and explain how

6G-RUPA offers a viable foundation for topology-aware, low-state routing in highly dynamic NTN environments.

2.1. The LEO Networking Environment: Dynamics and Constraints

The operational environment of LEO constellations is characterized by a unique set of distinctive physical dynamics and stringent resource constraints, which render traditional networking approaches largely ineffective.

LEO satellites must travel at high velocities to maintain their orbits, which causes their orbital periods to be 128 minutes or less. The rapid relative motion among LEO satellites is the primary factor behind the frequent and dynamic changes in the LEO network topology. For a stationary user on the ground, a satellite in an operational constellation such as Starlink remains visible for approximately two to eight minutes per pass, depending on minimum elevation angle [16], thus requiring frequent handovers. While ISLs within the same orbital plane are stable from satellites' perspective, links between different orbital planes are in constant flux, breaking and reforming as satellites move, particularly at the polar "seams" of the constellation. Unlike the unpredictable failures terrestrial protocols are designed for, this topological change is the network's normal, predictable state of operation.

Satellites are severely power-constrained systems, relying on solar panels for power generation and rechargeable batteries for storage, especially during eclipse periods when they are in Earth's shadow [17]. A significant operational challenge arises from the inherent mismatch between the uniform global distribution of satellite capacity and the highly non-uniform distribution of user demand, which is concentrated over landmasses and sparse over oceans [2].

This leads to massive overprovisioning, with a large fraction of the constellation consuming power while carrying little or no traffic at any given moment. This inefficiency makes energy-aware routing a critical concern. The problem is compounded by the power demands of the routing hardware itself. High-performance routers rely on TCAM for fast packet forwarding, but TCAMs are highly power-intensive, with consumption growing with the size of the routing table [18].

Therefore, a routing protocol that generates large forwarding tables directly increases the power draw, which can shorten a satellite's mission life, making forwarding state minimization a critical design goal.

To illustrate this constraint, consider a typical broadband LEO satellite. Modern high-density battery packs (e.g., NMC 2170 cells, exceeding 230

Wh/kg) yield roughly 11 kWh of on-board capacity, and depth-of-discharge caps of about 50%, enforced to preserve battery lifespan over a multi-year mission, leave at most 5.5 kWh for each roughly 30-minute eclipse period [19, 20]. Within this envelope, any persistent power draw competes directly with mission lifetime. Forwarding state is one such draw to the extent that lookup-hardware power grows with table size [18, 4, 21]: the evaluation in Section 4 shows that destination-oriented link-state routing requires hundreds to thousands of forwarding entries per satellite, whereas the proposed topological scheme requires fewer than five on average. We deliberately do not translate this state gap into watt-level savings, since such translations depend on router implementation details and on the fraction of spacecraft power consumed by forwarding hardware. The battery discussion defines the power envelope within which routing efficiency matters; it is not a measured spacecraft-power result.

2.2. Inter-Satellite Link Scenarios

The physical topology of a LEO constellation is defined by its ISLs. The design of this ISL topology directly impacts network stability and routing complexity. While various topology designs are possible, two scenarios are particularly common in practice [22, 23], as illustrated in Figure 1a and Figure 1b:

- **Two ISLs per satellite (Intra-plane, ring)** In the simplest configuration, each satellite maintains two ISLs, connecting to the satellite immediately ahead and behind it within the same orbital plane. As the relative distance between satellites in the same orbit is approximately fixed, these intra-plane links are highly stable and can be maintained permanently. This provides a basic, linear connectivity path along each orbit but offers no direct paths between different orbital planes. This setup is showcased in Figure 1a.
- **Four ISLs per satellite (Intra-plane and Inter-plane, +Grid):** A more robust and common design, often referred to as a "+Grid" topology, equips each satellite with four ISLs. This includes the two stable intra-plane links plus two inter-plane links connecting to the nearest satellites in each of the two adjacent orbital planes. This creates a resilient grid-like mesh, enabling more direct routing paths across the entire constellation. These inter-plane links can be strategically

targeted; for instance, connecting satellite n in plane p to satellite n in planes $p - 1$ and $p + 1$ provides strong East-West connectivity, which is highly valuable for connecting major population centers in the Northern Hemisphere [24]. This setup is illustrated in Figure 1b. Handley et al. [22] provide a detailed analysis of how the +Grid topology improves path diversity and reduces latency compared to ring-only topologies.

Figure 1: Representative regular ISL topologies used throughout the paper. The Ring case keeps only intra-plane adjacency, whereas the +Grid case adds one left and one right inter-plane neighbor while preserving the intra-plane links.

2.3. Architectural Frameworks for Satellite Networking

Having described the physical topology of LEO constellations, we now consider how different architectural frameworks propose to build a functional network on top of it. The choice of protocol stack for ISLs is a fundamental design decision that directly impacts routing complexity, scalability, and the degree to which the satellite constellation is integrated with the terrestrial network. In practice, three representative frameworks are especially relevant to the discussion in this paper: the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) regenerative framework, the commercial Direct-to-Cell (D2C) framework, and the 6G-RUPA framework.

The 3GPP regenerative framework. The 3GPP has progressively integrated NTN into the 5G New Radio (NR) standard. Release 17 finalized the first NTN specifications, primarily for the *transparent* (bent-pipe) architecture, where the satellite acts as an analog RF repeater and all higher-layer processing (Media Access Control (MAC), Radio Link Control (RLC), Packet

Figure 2: 6G-RUPA recursive user-plane stack for an integrated 5G/NTN deployment. Columns show UE, 5G-AN, three on-board GUPFs, the ground GUPF, and the data network. Rows show the recursive scopes *Application* (end-to-end UE–DN), the *PDU* layer of the PDU Session (UE up to the User Plane Function (UPF) acting as PDU Session Anchor, per 3GPP TS 23.501 §8.3.1), *LEO AN*, and *LEO Backbone*. The ground GUPF/PSA terminates the PDU-session layer and provides DN access over N6. Lower rows show the underlying physical/link layers (5G-NR, L1/L2), and the bottom labels mark the 3GPP reference points N3, N9, and N6.

Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP)) remains at the ground-based gateway next generation Node B (gNB) [25, 26]. Releases 18 and 19 shifted toward the more ambitious *regenerative* architecture, in which the satellite hosts on-board gNB functions and performs packet processing in orbit. The most architecturally significant implication of this model is that ISLs between regenerative satellites are realized as Xn interfaces—the standard 3GPP inter-gNB signaling and data-forwarding interface [27]. In this framework, the satellite constellation becomes a seamless extension of the terrestrial Radio Access Network (RAN), with every inter-satellite hop carrying the full weight of the 3GPP protocol stack. While this provides deep integration with the terrestrial RAN and reuses existing mechanisms for mobility and session management, it also means that the complexity and overhead of those protocols—designed for comparatively static terrestrial deployments—must be sustained on every ISL, raising concerns about scalability and energy consumption across the satellite network.

Notably, 3GPP specifications already acknowledge both energy and scalability challenges in satellite networks. On the energy side, 3GPP focuses on User Equipment (UE) power optimizations, for example by using satellite coverage availability information to move terminals into idle or power-saving states before they leave coverage [28, 29]. On the scalability side, the specifications discuss the high system load, complexity, and memory overhead created by rapidly changing routing associations in LEO/Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) constellations, and recommend time-window-based pre-configuration driven by predictable orbital data to reduce feeder-link load, satellite CPU load, and memory usage [29]. However, these mitigations primarily address control-plane and signaling overhead rather than the forwarding-state scalability problem that motivates this work.

The commercial D2C framework. A fundamentally different model is exemplified by SpaceX’s Starlink D2C service¹, deployed in partnership with terrestrial mobile operators such as T-Mobile in the US and MasOrange in Spain. Rather than waiting for full 3GPP NTN standardization, Starlink pursued an early-deployment strategy by integrating conventional LTE evolved Node B (eNB) payloads into its satellites, complemented with proprietary adaptations for satellite operation such as software-defined compensation for Doppler shift and timing advance [30]. This non-3GPP NTN-

¹<https://starlink.com/es/business/direct-to-cell>

compliant framework allows unmodified LTE smartphones to connect directly to the spaceborne base station, perceiving it as a standard terrestrial cell tower. On the backhaul side, the inter-satellite backbone operates over a proprietary Internet Protocol version 6 (IPv6)-over-laser mesh, where user data is encapsulated in GTP-U/UDP/IP tunnels and routed across the constellation via ISLs before reaching the terrestrial mobile-network core. This pragmatic design avoids the overhead of running Xn on every ISL and has enabled rapid commercial deployment, but it inherits the fundamental limitations of IP routing in a dynamic topology: the need for large routing tables, frequent reconvergence, and the conflation of identity and location in the address [29].

The 6G-RUPA framework. The approach proposed in this paper is grounded in the 6G-RUPA framework [8], which offers an alternative architecture that remains backward compatible with existing Transmission Control Protocol (TCP)/IP-based systems while enabling mechanisms better suited to dynamic LEO environments. Rather than forcing IP onto ISLs, 6G-RUPA employs the Error and Flow Control Protocol (EFCP) with scope-specific policies at every layer [8, 9], providing an evolutionary path that can coexist with current infrastructure. In this framework, the user-plane function is realized through a GUPF with only the minimal common functionalities, while the policies at each scope can be tailored to the satellite environment. The same architecture has recently been shown to reduce GUPF forwarding state to $\mathcal{O}(1)$ complexity—independent of the number of attached terminals—in national-grade terrestrial operator cores through topological address aggregation [10]; the present paper applies the same topological-addressing principle to the constellation-backbone scope, where the structure being exploited is orbital rather than administrative. Figure 2 summarizes this layered view. The key insight is that a single recursive protocol operates across all segments, but with policies adapted to each scope’s specific requirements. The access scope can prioritize reliability and handover resilience, while the backbone scope can use lightweight, topology-aware policies—such as the topological addressing scheme proposed in this paper—that minimize forwarding state and energy consumption. This recursive, policy-driven approach avoids both the overhead of full 3GPP signaling on every ISL and the architectural limitations of IP-based routing in a dynamic environment.

This comparison motivates the rest of the paper. The proposed scheme leverages the addressing flexibility of 6G-RUPA to overcome the routing challenges of LEO constellations while moving beyond the legacy assumption that

the satellite backbone must behave like a conventional IP subnet.

2.4. Limitations of IP and Routing Protocols for LEO Satellite Constellations

Routing within LEO constellations is challenging due to the dynamically evolving network topology. While satellite motion is largely deterministic, the resulting link dynamics (e.g., changing neighbor sets, intermittent ISLs, and frequent user/satellite handovers) violate key assumptions incorporated into the current Internet architecture and its dominant intra-domain routing protocols [22, 31].

At the addressing level, the classical Internet model uses the concept of an IP address simultaneously as an identifier ("who") and as a topological locator ("where") [32]. In LEO systems, attachment points can change on the order of minutes; therefore, binding an endpoint address to the serving satellite or beam would require frequent renumbering. This, in turn, disrupts long-lived transport sessions, which are typically designed for more stable networking environments such as terrestrial networks, and complicates reachability [33]. Existing workarounds typically rely on indirection (anchors) or tunneling, preserving session continuity at the cost of additional state, longer paths, and extra encapsulation overhead.

At the routing level, link-state protocols such as OSPF are engineered for networks where topology changes rarely occur and the steady state is stable. In LEO, however, change is the steady state: even when dynamics are predictable, a link-state control plane must continuously disseminate updates and repeatedly run shortest-path recomputations, consuming scarce control-plane bandwidth on ISLs and increasing transient inconsistency [31, 34, 2]. Moreover, classical link-state requires each node to maintain a global topology database and compute a complete forwarding table, which is costly for satellites with constrained compute, memory, and energy budgets [17]. At the data plane, those routes are then realized through destination-prefix forwarding, typically implemented with longest-prefix matching. In large constellations, this further couples scalability to forwarding-table growth, since each node must store sizable destination-oriented state in lookup structures that are often power-limited, making energy and memory pressure first-order design constraints rather than implementation details [4, 21].

Both limitations have been attacked before, in two largely separate research threads. On the addressing side, identity-locator separation has been

standardized for terrestrial networks in protocols such as Locator/ID Separation Protocol (LISP) [35] and ILNP [36], which decouple stable endpoint identifiers from routable locators at the cost of a mapping or rendezvous system that must track locator changes. On the routing side, early LEO research exploited constellation regularity directly: the distributed datagram routing algorithm of Ekici et al. forwards on virtual $(plane, slot)$ coordinates with purely local decisions [11], Henderson and Katz studied distributed geographic-based forwarding [12], and virtual-topology and virtual-node schemes mask orbital motion behind a fixed logical graph [13, 14]. These approaches demonstrated that low-state topological forwarding is viable in regular constellations, but each was designed as a self-contained protocol for an isolated satellite system, with metrics and forwarding rules tailored to that specific constellation model, without integration into a terrestrial-NTN user plane, and without an architectural mechanism for absorbing ground-endpoint mobility.

Together, these limitations motivate approaches that combine the two threads: (i) decouple stable identities from time-varying locations, as in LISP/ILNP but without bolting a mapping overlay onto an addressing model that resists it, and (ii) exploit the structured, predictable geometry of constellations to reduce per-node forwarding state and control-plane overhead, as in classical topological LEO routing but as a reusable policy rather than a bespoke protocol. The scheme proposed in this paper follows this combined direction within the 6G-RUPA architecture, and additionally captures the physical asymmetry of inter-plane ISLs with a pivot-weighted estimator computed from measured edge weights, generalizing to arbitrary measured geometry the constellation-specific analytic delay refinement that classical datagram routing applied only to an idealized Walker model.

3. 6G-RUPA’s Addressing Scheme & Topological Routing for LEO Satellites

This section is organized from addressing to forwarding. First, the principle of topological addressing is introduced. Next, the proposed 6G-RUPA address structure for LEO constellations is defined. Finally, the forwarding rule is derived in four steps: the regular Ring/+Grid logical space is modeled as a discrete torus, the physical asymmetry of LEO ISLs is made explicit, the pivot estimator is introduced as a geometric refinement, and the resulting local forwarding rule is stated.

Topological routing is motivated by the need to avoid destination-oriented forwarding tables in large and highly dynamic LEO constellations. Instead of computing and storing routes to all destinations, each satellite forwards packets using only local neighbor knowledge and the logical structure of the constellation. This is possible because, although the physical geometry evolves continuously, the logical structure of the constellation remains stable. In a +Grid topology, for example, each satellite keeps the same four logical neighbors (ahead, behind, left, and right); during a polar crossing, the physical orientation of those neighbors may change, but their logical identities do not (see Figure 1b).

Figure 3: Representative LEO constellation snapshots generated with the LEOPath CesiumJS viewer (interactive version available at <https://fundacio-i2cat.github.io/LEOPath/cesium/>). The panels show the same constellation at three simulation instants, illustrating the continuous physical topology drift that motivates routing-state stability and churn analysis.

Supplementary Video 1 (referenced here; placed alongside this figure in the online article) shows the LEOPath viewer in motion: it switches between Ring and +Grid ISL topologies, overlays a live topological-forwarding route alongside the link-state shortest path for the same source-destination pair, and repeats the comparison across constellations, illustrating that the pivot-weighted route tracks the shortest path closely while using only a handful of forwarding entries per satellite.

3.1. The Principle of Topological Addressing

The core idea of topological addressing is therefore to encode a node’s logical position directly into its address. In a regular topology such as a +Grid LEO mesh (see Figure 1b), this allows forwarding to become a local

distance-minimization step rather than a lookup in a large routing table. To address the forwarding-state and energy challenges identified in Section 1, we therefore encode each satellite’s logical position directly into its 6G-RUPA address. Packets are then forwarded greedily to the neighbor with minimum topological distance, replacing network-wide routing tables with local neighbor knowledge. Traffic-engineering or failure-handling policies can still override this default behavior when needed.

3.2. 6G-RUPA Addressing Scheme for LEO Satellites

An addressing scheme specifically designed for LEO satellite constellations is proposed. Each address is hierarchical in that it is represented as a four-tuple:

$$A = (sh, o, st, x), \tag{1}$$

where:

- *sh* represents the **shell** identifier, a logical grouping of orbits that share similar characteristics (e.g., altitude, inclination).
- *o* represents the **orbital plane** identifier within the shell.
- *st* represents the **satellite slot** within the orbit.
- *x* is a node type identifier: $x = 0$ if the node designates the satellite itself, and $x = 1$ for a ground station (GS) currently attached to that satellite.

This structure maps each network address to a satellite’s logical location in the constellation graph. At this stage, the address should be read simply as a compact coordinate label: it says which shell, plane, satellite slot, and attached endpoint the packet is trying to reach. The next subsection explains why this coordinate label can also be used as a forwarding guide. In short, for regular Ring and +Grid topologies, one logical hop corresponds to a one-step change in one address coordinate, so reducing address distance also reduces graph distance, hence reducing address distance to the destination also reduces the number of hops to reach it. For more complex topologies, this principle still holds for the majority of cases, but additional policies are needed to handle exceptions, as explained in Section 3.3.

Figure 4: Topological addressing scheme for LEO satellite constellations. The four-tuple $A = (sh, o, st, x)$ is read from left to right: a shell, an orbital plane within that shell, a satellite slot within that plane, and either the satellite itself ($x = 0$) or an attached ground station ($x = 1$). In the regular Ring/+Grid topologies evaluated here, the orbital-plane and satellite-slot fields provide the coordinates used by the torus forwarding scores.

3.3. Routing Algorithm

This subsection derives the forwarding rule from the constellation’s logical coordinates. The development separates four roles. First, δ_{hop} defines the base metric on the regular Ring/+Grid logical space and gives the hop-optimality argument. Second, the non-uniform physical weights of LEO ISLs explain why a pure hop metric is insufficient for distance stretch. Third, δ_{pivot} refines the logical metric by optimizing over a pivot slot. Fourth, the local next-hop rule combines the measured first-hop weight with the pivot estimate to select a neighbor without a global routing table.

Consider a satellite S_i in a +Grid topology with four ISLs: two intra-plane neighbors, S_{i-1} and S_{i+1} , and two inter-plane neighbors, S_j and S_k , as shown in Figure 5. Given a destination address $A_{dst} = (sh_{dst}, o_{dst}, st_{dst}, x_{dst})$, S_i evaluates a mode-specific score for each neighbor and forwards the packet to the neighbor with the minimum score.

The main instantiation of the proposed forwarding algorithm targets the single-shell regular Ring and +Grid topologies evaluated in this paper. In this setting the relevant forwarding coordinates are the orbital-plane index o and the satellite-slot field st ; for compactness, the equations below denote that slot coordinate by s . The node-type field x identifies whether the final endpoint is the satellite itself or an attached GS. The algorithm therefore uses distances over (o, s) . A more general multi-shell deployment could still use a hierarchical fallback score that gives priority to shell, then plane, then

Figure 5: Satellite S_i with 4 ISLs in a +Grid topology. Connections include intra-plane neighbors (S_{i-1}, S_{i+1}) and inter-plane neighbors (S_j, S_k).

slot differences, but that fallback is not the distance used for the evaluated Ring/+Grid results.

3.3.1. Greedy Forwarding in the Logical Torus

The first layer is deliberately unweighted. It establishes that the address space is not only a locator space but also a valid routing space in the regular logical topologies. For the regular +Grid case, each satellite is identified by logical coordinates $(o, s) \in \mathbb{Z}_O \times \mathbb{Z}_S$, where O is the number of orbital planes and S is the number of satellites per plane. The resulting graph is the Cartesian product $C_O \square C_S$: one cycle follows the orbital-plane dimension, and one cycle follows the satellite-slot dimension. Equivalently, it is a discrete torus graph, namely a rectangular logical grid with periodic boundary conditions in both dimensions, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Regular +Grid edges connect (o, s) to $(o, s \pm 1)$ and $(o \pm 1, s)$, modulo the corresponding dimensions. Under these assumptions, the coordinate map $S_i \mapsto (o_i, s_i)$ defines a graph isomorphism between the satellite graph and $C_O \square C_S$: one hop in the satellite graph is exactly a one-step change in one

Figure 6: Logical view of the regular +Grid topology as the Cartesian product of two cycles, also called a discrete torus graph. The grid has one cycle over orbital planes and one cycle over satellite slots; representative wrap-around links close the two dimensions.

logical coordinate. The shortest-hop distance is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_{hop}(a, b) &= d_O(o_a, o_b) + d_S(s_a, s_b) \\
 &= \min(|o_a - o_b|, O - |o_a - o_b|) \\
 &\quad + \min(|s_a - s_b|, S - |s_a - s_b|).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where d_O and d_S denote the minimum cyclic separations in the orbital-plane and satellite-slot dimensions, respectively. Thus, δ_{hop} corresponds to the Manhattan (ℓ_1) distance on the discrete torus.

This expression applies the same cyclic-distance rule independently to both coordinates. For one cyclic coordinate with dimension N , the shortest separation between indices i and j is $\min(|i - j|, N - |i - j|)$. For example, if $S = 72$, slots 70 and 2 are separated by $\min(|70 - 2|, 72 - |70 - 2|) = 4$ hops rather than 68, because the shortest path crosses the cyclic boundary.

Lemma 1. *In the regular +Grid model, greedy forwarding with δ_{hop} achieves hop stretch equal to 1 for every reachable satellite pair.*

Lemma 1 is the classical Manhattan-distance property of torus product graphs, long exploited by logical-coordinate LEO routing [11]; we restate the short proof to keep the argument self-contained, since the weighted refinement in Section 3.3.2 builds directly on it.

Proof. Each +Grid edge changes exactly one cyclic coordinate by one step. Therefore, one hop can reduce δ_{hop} by at most one. If the current satellite is not the destination, at least one coordinate has non-zero cyclic distance to the destination; moving along the shortest direction in that coordinate is a valid neighbor move and reduces δ_{hop} by exactly one. Repeating this step reaches the destination in $\delta_{hop}(a, b)$ hops, and no path can use fewer hops because each hop reduces the distance by at most one. Thus each greedy step makes strict progress, loops are impossible, and the greedy path length equals the shortest-hop distance; equivalently, hop stretch is 1. \square

In the regular Ring case, the same argument applies within each orbital plane using the satellite-slot cycle C_S . Hence, δ_{hop} also gives a hop-optimal forwarding metric for the Ring topology, albeit with a simpler expression that only depends on the slot coordinate. However, for the +Grid case, the hop-optimality of δ_{hop} does not automatically imply that it is a good forwarding metric for physical distance, as explained in the next subsection.

3.3.2. Weighted Refinement for Physical Distance

The logical-hop result provides the proof anchor, but it is not the full engineering objective. Hop optimality does not automatically imply physical-distance optimality. Let $w(e)$ denote the physical length, or more generally the physical cost, of an ISL e . In regular +Grid constellations the logical graph is symmetric, but the physical embedding is not: the length of an inter-plane link depends on the satellite-slot index. We denote this deterministic slot-dependent cost by $w_{inter}(s)$. It decreases as adjacent orbital planes geometrically converge toward high-latitude regions, while it increases toward lower-latitude regions where the same plane separation subtends a larger distance. Consequently, several paths may minimize $\delta_{hop}(a, b)$ while having substantially different physical costs $\sum_e w(e)$. A forwarding metric that only counts hops cannot distinguish those equal-hop alternatives. This is precisely the regime that a purely hop-counting metric—such as the direction-estimation phase of Datagram Routing Algorithm (DRA) [11]—cannot resolve. Full DRA does address it, but through a closed-form direction-enhancement rule derived for an idealized equal-radius Walker model; the pivot-weighted estimator introduced next instead recovers physical-distance optimality directly from measured edge weights, on arbitrary geometry. Section 4.5 quantifies the stretch gap left by the hop-only metric. Figure 7 illustrates this physical asymmetry and the corresponding cost notation.

Figure 7: Physical asymmetry of inter-plane ISLs in a regular +Grid constellation. The logical graph gives the same hop count for all inter-plane moves, but the physical cost $w_{inter}(s)$ depends on slot s : adjacent planes are closer near high-latitude convergence regions than near lower latitudes. The pivot refinement uses this deterministic geometry through precomputable d_{intra} and d_{inter} costs.

The pivot refinement resolves this degeneracy by exploiting the deterministic geometry of the constellation rather than disseminating global link-state information. Define two precomputable cost functions for a homogeneous shell. First, $d_{intra}(s_1, s_2)$ is the shortest physical cost of moving within one orbital plane from slot s_1 to slot s_2 along the in-plane cycle. Second, $d_{inter}(o_1, o_2, r)$ is the shortest physical cost of crossing from plane o_1 to plane o_2 while remaining at slot r , i.e., along the inter-plane cycle induced by that slot. The estimator then assumes a three-phase path through a pivot slot r : move within the source plane to r , cross between planes at r , and move within the destination plane to the destination slot. Formally,

$$\delta_{pivot}(a, b) = \min_{r \in \mathbb{Z}_S} \{d_{intra}(s_a, r) + d_{inter}(o_a, o_b, r) + d_{intra}(r, s_b)\}. \quad (3)$$

This estimator keeps the mathematical structure of the torus while adding the physical asymmetry that matters for distance stretch. The minimization is a small $O(S)$ scan over precomputed deterministic geometry constants, not a shortest-path computation over the full network. In the primary evaluation, δ_{hop} supplies the analytical hop-optimal baseline, while δ_{pivot} is the practical refinement used to steer equal-hop decisions toward physically shorter high-latitude cross-links. The weighted score should therefore be read as a

geometric refinement of the hop-distance argument rather than as a standalone proof of weighted shortest-path optimality; the evaluation compares its delivered paths against shortest weighted paths in each snapshot.

3.3.3. Local Forwarding Rule

The runtime rule combines the first measured hop with the selected remaining-distance score. Let $d_m(A, A_{dst})$ denote the remaining address-space score selected by mode m : $d_m = \delta_{hop}$ for unit-torus hop mode and $d_m = \delta_{pivot}$ for pivot-weighted mode. For each neighbor $n \in \mathcal{N}(S_i)$ with address A_n , the satellite forms

$$q_m(n; S_i, A_{dst}) = c_m(S_i, n) + d_m(A_n, A_{dst}),$$

where

$$c_m(S_i, n) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{unit-torus hop mode,} \\ w(S_i, n), & \text{pivot-weighted mode.} \end{cases}$$

The forwarding decision is

$$next_hop_m \in \arg \min_{n \in \mathcal{N}(S_i)} q_m(n; S_i, A_{dst}).$$

Figure 8 shows this local neighbor-scoring step for the pivot-weighted mode. Thus, the first-hop term is absent from the pure hop metric and appears only when the score estimates physical path length. If several neighbors attain the same minimum, a fixed deterministic tie-breaker is applied. Each satellite compares only its immediate neighbors, so forwarding state remains tied to local degree rather than constellation size. The per-hop decision cost is $O(k)$ for degree k in unit-torus mode and $O(kS)$ in pivot-weighted mode; in the evaluated Ring and +Grid regimes, k is bounded by two or four, so the weighted decision reduces to a small $O(S)$ scan over precomputed deterministic geometry constants. Link-state routing, by contrast, requires $O(N)$ forwarding state per satellite and relies on maintaining a global view of the network.

3.3.4. Irregular Topologies and Exception Policies

The preceding argument is intentionally limited to regular logical models. If operational policies remove predictable sets of links, for example around polar inter-plane deactivation zones or counter-rotating seams, the graph is

Figure 8: Local forwarding decision at satellite S_i . Both candidate routes to destination $B = A_{dst}$ reach it in the same number of hops, so a pure hop metric cannot separate them. The pivot-weighted score $q(n) = w(S_i, n) + \delta_{pivot}(A_n, A_{dst})$ adds the measured first-hop weight and the deterministic remaining-distance estimate, steering the decision toward the neighbor n^* on the physically shorter path, using only local neighbor addresses.

no longer an exact product of cycles. Greedy forwarding can then encounter a local minimum at the boundary of a geometric void.

Across the evaluated constellations and all reachable satellite pairs in the corresponding regular Ring/+Grid snapshot graphs, we did not observe any case in which the greedy forwarding rule failed to find a route: as quantified in Section 4.5, more than 850,000 delivered forwarding walks completed without a routing loop or greedy local minimum. This empirical observation should not be read as a universal guarantee for seam-deactivated or failure-impaired deployments.

In 6G-RUPA, such irregular cases can be handled by EFCP exception policies layered on top of the default forwarding rule [9]. Rather than matching destination prefixes, an exception rule can match the destination topological region or address-tuple interval shadowed by the void and force one or more detour hops before greedy forwarding resumes. The default forwarding state remains $O(k)$, where k is the local degree; additional exception state scales with the number of configured boundary exceptions e_b , which may itself grow with the size of the seam or void being handled.

Algorithm 1 provides pseudocode for the topological routing forwarding decision at a single satellite². It first selects the destination satellite or ground-station egress address, then evaluates immediate neighbors with the selected address-space score.

The key property of this algorithm is its *local-state* nature: each satellite only needs its own address and the addresses of its immediate neighbors, obtained during ISL setup. No full-network routing table is required for default forwarding. The selected mode m determines both the remaining score d_m and the first-hop term c_m : unit-torus forwarding compares only $d_m(A_n, A_{dst})$, whereas pivot-weighted forwarding adds the measured first-hop ISL weight. The deterministic tie-breaker is used only when local scores are flat; it is not a separate route-computation mechanism.

4. Evaluation Methodology and Validation Framework

Hypatia is a LEO satellite network simulation framework that provides the core constellation and orbital modeling needed to study dynamic satellite systems [37, 38]. Our goal in this paper is not to claim protocol-faithful

²https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath/tree/main/leopath/network_state/routing_algorithms/topological_routing

Algorithm 1 Topological Routing Forwarding Decision at Satellite S_i

Require: \mathcal{D} : Candidate destination satellite/egress addresses (A_e, ℓ_e) A_{curr} : Current satellite's own address $(sh_i, o_i, st_i, 0)$ \mathcal{N} : Neighbor tuples $(n, I_n, w_{i,n})$ with valid ISLs m : Selected distance mode with score d_m and first-hop term c_m **Ensure:** Next hop interface for forwarding the packet

```
1: if  $\mathcal{D} = \emptyset$  then
2:   return  $\perp$  ▷ No visible destination egress
3: end if
4:  $(A_{dst}, \ell_{dst}) \leftarrow \arg \min_{(A_e, \ell_e) \in \mathcal{D}} (d_m(A_{curr}, A_e) + \ell_e)$ 
5:  $d_{curr} \leftarrow d_m(A_{curr}, A_{dst})$ 
6: if  $d_{curr} = 0$  then ▷ Destination satellite or selected egress is current satellite
7:   return GSL_Interface
8: end if
9:  $best\_neighbor \leftarrow \text{None}$ 
10:  $best\_score \leftarrow \infty$ 
11:  $best\_interface \leftarrow \text{None}$ 
12:  $best\_tie \leftarrow (\infty, \infty, \infty)$ 
13: for  $(n, I_n, w_{i,n}) \in \mathcal{N}$  do ▷ Evaluate all neighbors
14:    $A_n \leftarrow \text{TopologicalAddress}(n)$ 
15:    $d_n \leftarrow d_m(A_n, A_{dst})$ 
16:    $q_n \leftarrow c_m(S_i, n) + d_n$ 
17:    $\tau_n \leftarrow \text{TieBreak}(A_n, A_{dst})$ 
18:   if  $q_n < best\_score$  or  $(q_n = best\_score \text{ and } \tau_n < best\_tie)$  then
19:      $best\_score \leftarrow q_n$ 
20:      $best\_neighbor \leftarrow n$ 
21:      $best\_interface \leftarrow I_n$ 
22:      $best\_tie \leftarrow \tau_n$ 
23:   end if
24: end for
25: if  $best\_neighbor \neq \text{None}$  then
26:   return  $best\_interface$ 
27: else
28:   return InvokeEFCPEXception $(A_{dst})$  ▷ No usable neighbor; drop only if no exception policy exists
29: end if

30: function TIEBREAK $(A_n, A_{dst})$ 
31:    $p \leftarrow 0$  if  $o_n = o_{dst}$  else 1
32:   return  $(p, (st_{dst} - st_n) \bmod S, (o_{dst} - o_n) \bmod O)$ 
33: end function
```

emulation of deployed routing stacks, but to validate concrete implementations of analytically defined routing algorithms under realistic constellation dynamics. To support that objective, we developed LEOPath [15]³, an open-source Python simulator built on top of Hypatia that preserves its core orbital machinery while extending it with pluggable routing modules, configurable ground-satellite link (GSL) attachment policies, and detailed forwarding-state export for time-series analysis. Recent work on integrated NTN traffic management has taken a similar approach, using LRSIM, an earlier name for LEOPath, to evaluate dynamic traffic-management decisions [39].

Key features of LEOPath relevant to this study include:

- Modular protocol implementation: routing logic is decoupled from the simulation core, making new algorithms straightforward to implement and compare.
- Configurable constellation generation: experiments are defined through simple YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML) files and can use real Two-Line Element (TLE) data or synthetic constellations generated with the Simplified General Perturbations 4 (SGP4) propagator.
- Dynamic topology and forwarding-state analysis: the simulator exports time-series forwarding-state logs at each time step (`[source, destination, next_hop]`), enabling precise analysis of route dynamics and state scalability.
- Dynamic ISL/GSL management: inter-satellite and ground-to-satellite links are updated automatically based on visibility and distance constraints, with support for multiple GSs and attachment policies.
- Visualization support: LEOPath provides an interactive CesiumJS constellation viewer (see Figure 3 and the companion demo at <https://fundacio-i2cat.github.io/LEOPath/cesium/>) that renders satellite positions, ISLs, GSLs, and orbital motion directly in the browser.

LEOPath focuses on topology evolution and routing-state generation, not packet-level simulation. This is an intentional scope choice: the present paper validates forwarding-state, route-instability, and path-quality properties

³<https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath>

of the routing families under dynamic orbital evolution, but it does not claim results for queueing delay, packet drops, jitter, congestion response, or transport throughput. For end-to-end traffic studies, its forwarding-state output can be integrated with packet-level simulators such as ns-3, following the workflow used in Hypatia [37].

This gives us a controlled validation environment in which the implementations of the studied routing algorithms can be exercised against realistic satellite motion and attachment dynamics, and their observed behavior can be checked against the analytical expectations developed in the following section.

4.1. Evaluation Overview

This section evaluates the proposed topological forwarding algorithm from Section 3.3 against two additional routing families currently represented in LEOPath: a link-state and an explicit-path routing algorithm. The evaluation proceeds in three steps. First, we state how the proposed algorithm and the two benchmark families are instantiated in the simulator. Second, we define the primary metrics used to compare them. Third, we use LEOPath to validate those instantiations under time-varying LEO topology dynamics. Broader architectural implications such as routing-update complexity, derived update burden, and packet-header overhead are then discussed separately in Section 5.

Each simulation spans a six-hour orbital window with one-minute sampling intervals, yielding 360 topology snapshots per run. We establish a comprehensive evaluation matrix comparing all three routing families (link-state, topological forwarding, and the explicit-path algorithm) across four commercial constellation configurations (Starlink, OneWeb, Kuiper, and Telesat) under both ISL connectivity regimes (Ring and +Grid). Within this shared matrix, the explicit-path algorithm is reported primarily with $R = 3$ dynamic final-egress repair, which reuses the cached core path while locally resolving the final destination handoff. We retain strict $R = 3$ as a sensitivity point and use $R = 1$ only as a sanity-control case showing that per-snapshot explicit planning recovers shortest-path quality.

The remainder of this section is organized as follows. Section 4.2 presents the simulation instantiations and benchmark variants. Section 4.3 defines the evaluation metrics. Section 4.4 then describes the LEOPath validation setup used to instantiate those algorithms over dynamic constellations. Section 4.5 presents and discusses the results.

4.2. Routing Algorithms

The proposed topological algorithm is defined in Section 3.3; this subsection only states the simulation instantiation used for that algorithm and the three benchmark families used for comparison: a destination-oriented link-state baseline, a hop-only logical-coordinate baseline (the direction-estimation phase of DRA), and an explicit-path family. Table 1 summarizes the corresponding modules; all are available as pluggable components in LEOPath⁴.

We use a small amount of common notation to describe the three routing families. Let \mathcal{S} be the set of satellites and \mathcal{G} the set of ground stations. At snapshot t , i.e., a concrete time instant, the satellite backbone is the weighted graph

$$G_t = (\mathcal{S}, E_t, w_t),$$

where $(u, v) \in E_t$ when an ISL between satellites u and v is available at time t , and $w_t(u, v) > 0$ is the corresponding link cost (here, physical distance). Let $N_t(s) = \{u \in \mathcal{S} : (s, u) \in E_t\}$ denote the neighbor set of satellite s . Ground-station mobility is captured by an attachment map

$$\alpha_t : \mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathcal{S} \cup \{\perp\},$$

where $\alpha_t(g) = \perp$ means that ground station g is disconnected. For a reachable ground-station destination $g \in \mathcal{G}$, the effective satellite target is $d_t(g) = \alpha_t(g)$. Routing inside the satellite backbone is therefore defined over destination satellites. For link-state and topological forwarding, the forwarding decision is represented by a next-hop map

$$\phi_t^{(r)} : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{S} \cup \{\text{local}, \perp\},$$

where $r \in \{\text{LS}, \text{TF}\}$ denotes the routing family, $\phi_t^{(r)}(s, d) = \text{local}$ means that $s = d$, and $\phi_t^{(r)}(s, d) = \perp$ means that no forwarding decision exists. End-to-end forwarding is then obtained by composing the backbone forwarding rule with the attachment map.

Figure 9 summarizes this notation on a small snapshot graph and illustrates how the three routing families interpret the same topology.

i) *Link-State*⁵

⁴https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath/tree/main/leopath/network_state/routing_algorithms

⁵https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath/tree/main/leopath/network_state/routing_algorithms/shortest_path_link_state_routing

Figure 9: Snapshot graph notation. Satellites \mathcal{S} form the backbone $G_t = (\mathcal{S}, E_t, w_t)$, where each ISL $e \in E_t$ carries a physical cost $w_t(e)$. Ground stations g, g' attach to their nearest visible satellites via α_t ; the neighbor set $N_t(s)$ contains satellites adjacent to s through active ISLs.

The link-state family assumes full knowledge of G_t . For any $s, d \in \mathcal{S}$, let

$$P_t^*(s, d) \in \arg \min_{P: s \rightsquigarrow d} \sum_{(u,v) \in P} w_t(u, v)$$

be a minimum-cost path from s to d in G_t , whenever such a path exists. The link-state forwarding rule is then

$$\phi_t^{(\text{LS})}(s, d) = \begin{cases} \text{local}, & s = d, \\ \text{first}(P_t^*(s, d)), & s \neq d \text{ and } d \text{ is reachable from } s, \\ \perp, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Accordingly, each satellite maintains one destination-oriented forwarding entry per reachable destination satellite, so the forwarding state at each satellite scales as $O(|\mathcal{S}|)$. In the current LEOPath implementation, all pairs $P_t^*(s, d)$ are computed at each snapshot using Floyd–Warshall because the evaluation requires full snapshot-wide forwarding state; repeated single-source Dijkstra runs would define the same routing family.

ii) Topological Forwarding

The topological-forwarding runs use Algorithm 1. The primary matrix instantiates the algorithm with the pivot-weighted discrete-torus score δ_{pivot} from Section 3.3.2; hop-count reasoning is checked against the unit torus score

δ_{hop} from Equation 2. Ground-station destinations inherit the (sh, o, st) tuple of their currently serving satellite $\alpha_t(g)$, so handovers are represented as destination-locator renumbering at the attachment boundary. In other words, satellites never change their addresses, only ground stations change addresses when they attach to a new satellite: they get an address from the subnetwork of satellite s . For state accounting, deterministic geometry parameters used by δ_{pivot} are not counted as per-destination forwarding entries; the installed state is the local neighbor-address information required by Algorithm 1.

iii) *Hop-only logical-coordinate baseline (DRA direction-estimation phase)*⁶

To isolate the pivot-weighted metric’s contribution from that of topological forwarding in general, we include a hop-only logical-coordinate baseline: the direction-estimation phase of DRA, due to Ekici et al. [11]. Full DRA is delay-aware—it follows minimum-*hop* estimation on the logical grid with a *direction-enhancement* phase that refines the next hop using the latitude-dependent physical length of inter-plane ISLs to approximate minimum-propagation-delay paths; the original authors report this enhancement is essential, dropping mean deviation from the minimum-delay path from above 8% to below 0.3%. That enhancement is a closed-form rule derived for an idealized equal-radius Walker constellation, however, and does not transfer to measured TLE-derived geometry, the +Grid seam, or ground-station-anchored locators. Our baseline reproduces the estimation phase only: identical logical (o, s) coordinates, decision locality, and table-free forwarding as the proposed scheme, but scored with the unit-torus hop metric δ_{hop} at no first-hop weight ($c_m = 0$), blind to inter-plane ISL length. We label it “Hop-only (δ_{hop})” in the result tables.

This makes the baseline a clean ablation of our own forwarding substrate: it differs from the proposed scheme in exactly one switch—the distance function—so any difference in delivered-path quality is attributable solely to the pivot-weighted refinement of Section 3.3.2, not to topological addressing as such. We therefore compare against DRA’s enhancement phase structurally rather than numerically: the pivot estimator recovers near-minimum-delay paths from *measured* edge weights on arbitrary geometry, including the seam case where DRA’s analytic model does not apply (Section 4.5).

⁶https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath/tree/main/leopath/network_state/routing_algorithms/dra_routing

iv) *Explicit-Path Algorithm*⁷

The explicit-path family separates route planning from forwarding by first selecting an end-to-end path and then reusing that path for subsequent forwarding decisions. Let $R \in \mathbb{N}$ denote the refresh interval in snapshots. At each planning instant $\tau \in \{0, R, 2R, \dots\}$ and for each source satellite $s \in \mathcal{S}$ and reachable destination ground station $g \in \mathcal{G}$, the algorithm chooses the planned egress satellite from the currently visible destination satellites:

$$d_\tau(s, g) = \arg \min_{x \in V_\tau(g)} (D_\tau^*(s, x) + \ell_\tau(x, g)),$$

where $V_\tau(g)$ is the set of satellites visible from g , $D_\tau^*(s, x)$ is the current shortest satellite-path distance from s to x , and $\ell_\tau(x, g)$ is the destination GSL distance. The planner then computes a path

$$\Pi_\tau(s, g) = \langle v_0 = s, v_1, \dots, v_m = d_\tau(s, g) \rangle.$$

Figure 10 visualizes this construction and the later reuse window.

Figure 10: Explicit-path algorithm planning and reuse. At a planning snapshot τ , the ingress satellite s chooses an egress $d_\tau(s, g)$ from the destination-visible set $V_\tau(g)$ and computes the carried path $\Pi_\tau(s, g)$. For the next R snapshots, packets reuse that cached core path. Strict mode succeeds only if the planned egress still sees the destination GS; dynamic final-egress mode keeps the cached core path but appends a local repair segment toward the current egress $d_t(g)$ when available.

⁷https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath/tree/main/leopath/network_state/routing_algorithms/explicit_path_routing

In the current implementation, $\Pi_\tau(s, g)$ is chosen from the current snapshot graph and then cached for the next R snapshots. Packets then carry a strict adjacency-style segment list derived from $\Pi_\tau(s, g)$, while forwarding nodes only need local neighbor/interface state to execute the carried path. The simulator supports two final-egress behaviors over the same cached core path: a strict mode that requires the planned destination egress to remain visible, and a dynamic final-egress mode that reuses the cached core path to the planned anchor but repairs only the last destination handoff toward a currently visible egress. Let $\widehat{\Pi}_{\tau,t}(s, g)$ denote the snapshot-effective path after this final-egress handling, and let $R_t(s, g) = P_t(d_\tau(s, g), d_t(g))$ be the dynamic repair path when such a current egress path exists:

$$\widehat{\Pi}_{\tau,t}(s, g) = \begin{cases} \Pi_\tau(s, g), & \text{strict success,} \\ \Pi_\tau(s, g) \oplus R_t(s, g), & \text{dynamic repair,} \\ \perp, & \text{failure.} \end{cases} \quad t \in [\tau, \tau + R - 1].$$

Strict success means that the planned egress remains in $V_t(g)$; dynamic repair means that a current visible egress and path from the cached anchor are available; \oplus appends the repair path without duplicating the anchor. The simulator materializes this family model as a compatibility first-hop mapping: if $\widehat{\Pi}_{\tau,t}(s, g) = \langle v_0 = s, v_1, \dots \rangle$, then $\tilde{\phi}_{\tau,t}^{(\text{EP})}(s, g) = v_1$; if the effective path has zero satellite hops, forwarding is local; otherwise delivery fails. At the family level, the essential property is that the path is selected explicitly and reused over one or more snapshots rather than recomputed greedily at every hop. In implementation terms, the measured forwarding state counts local neighbor/interface entries on all satellites plus installed destination-to-path ingress bindings only on satellites that currently serve ground-station attachments; packet-carried forwarding information is accounted for separately rather than folded into node-local state. For link-state and topological forwarding this carried information is the destination locator used by the forwarding rule. For the explicit-path algorithm it is the selected path stack, reported as an Segment Routing over IPv6 (SRv6) Segment Routing Header (SRH)-equivalent byte count in which each carried segment identifier is a 128-bit IPv6 address. Under the strict mode, cached plans whose destination egress no longer sees the GS are counted as explicit-path delivery failures rather than valid stretch samples. Under the dynamic final-egress mode, those cases are instead repaired through a locally resolved final segment whenever a current visible egress still exists; only residual no-egress

cases remain delivery failures. This is sufficient to measure forwarding state, state updates, delivered-path stretch, delivery failures, route-instability, and packet-carried forwarding information, but it is still not a protocol-faithful SRv6/SR-MPLS implementation. Its results should therefore be interpreted as evidence about the explicit-path family, not as proof for any single wire protocol.

4.3. Performance Evaluation Metrics

The algorithms are evaluated along three primary dimensions: forwarding state, satellite routing table updates, and path stretch. These metrics are defined at the algorithmic level and are then measured on the simulator outputs produced by the corresponding implementations. Together, they capture the data-plane footprint, router-local maintenance burden, and routing quality. In this context, routing quality refers to how closely an algorithm’s selected paths match the corresponding shortest paths in the same topology snapshot. We also report satellite-to-GS next-hop instability as a companion route-instability signal rather than as a direct count of routing table updates, and for the explicit-path algorithm we separately report delivery failures plus dynamic final-egress repair usage.

- **Forwarding state size** measures the number of forwarding-state units maintained at each satellite. This serves as a proxy for local memory cost, while intentionally avoiding a protocol-byte interpretation because the concrete encodings differ across families. For link-state, we count the number of routable satellite destinations represented in the topology graph. For topological forwarding, we count the local neighbor-address entries maintained in the satellite forwarding table, which scales with the node’s ISL degree k . For the explicit-path algorithm, we count local neighbor/interface entries on every satellite together with installed destination-to-path ingress bindings on satellites that currently host ground-station attachments; packet-carried forwarding-information bytes are discussed separately in Section 5.2. The per-satellite distribution at each snapshot is summarized using the mean and P95 values.
- **Satellite routing table updates** measure how much installed satellite-local state changes from one snapshot to the next. For each satellite, we compare the locally maintained forwarding state at snapshots $t - 1$ and

Table 1: Summary of Routing-Family Instantiations Used in the Primary 1-Minute Matrix

Algorithm	Core Mechanism	Key Characteristics
Link-State (Baseline)	Shortest-path forwarding from full snapshot topology knowledge.	Global state ($O(N)$). Shortest paths in each snapshot graph. Current validation implementation uses Floyd-Warshall each snapshot. Implementation ported from Hypatia.
Topological (Proposed)	Greedy forwarding via discrete-torus 6G-RUPA address distance.	Local state ($O(N_{neighbors})$). Local neighbor evaluation per destination.
Hop-only (δ_{hop}) (Prior-art metric [11])	Greedy forwarding via unit-hop logical-coordinate distance (δ_{hop} , no physical weight); the direction-estimation phase of DRA [11], without its delay-enhancement phase.	Local state ($O(N_{neighbors})$). Metric ablation of the proposed scheme: identical except the distance function ignores ISL physical length.
Explicit-Path Algorithm (Benchmark)	Source-selected paths reused for R snapshots toward the planned egress.	Per-family ingress state ($O(k + i_s)$, where k is local degree and i_s counts installed ingress bindings at satellite s). Source-selected explicit paths reused across R snapshots. Packet-carried forwarding information.

t and count additions, deletions, and modifications; the reported mean totals therefore approximate the number of routing table updates per satellite and snapshot. This is the primary router-local maintenance metric in the present paper because it measures actual installed-state mutations rather than just route-outcome changes.

- **Path stretch** compares the routing quality of each algorithm’s chosen path against the shortest path on the same snapshot graph. For every communicating GS pair, we compute both the satellite-backbone distance stretch and the hop-count stretch between the pair’s attachment satellites:

$$\text{stretch} = \frac{L_{\text{algo}}}{L_{\text{opt}}},$$

where L_{opt} is the shortest corresponding backbone length in the same snapshot, using physical ISL distance for distance stretch and hop count for hop-count stretch. If both GSs attach to the same satellite, the backbone path has zero length and we assign stretch 1 by convention. For explicit-path routing, strict cached plans whose chosen egress no longer sees the destination GS are reported as delivery failures rather than included as stretch samples. In the dynamic final-egress sensitivity, the delivered path includes the repaired final segment toward the current visible egress. A stretch of 1.0 indicates shortest-path routing for delivered paths; values above 1.0 quantify the detour penalty introduced by the algorithm.

To deeply interpret route stability without distorting our primary evaluation, we track a set of standalone companion diagnostics. These metrics isolate the root causes of network instability by decoupling algorithmic path changes from physical environmental changes:

- **Algorithmic Path Volatility:**
 - *Satellite-to-GS Next-Hop Instability:* Measures the fraction of transit satellite routing entries targeting a destination GS that alter their selected next hop between snapshots. This captures pure path-flapping within the backbone.
 - *Effective Next-Hop Instability:* A foundational metric tracking any generic next-hop mutation across snapshots $t - 1$ and t .

- **Physical & Environmental Dynamics:**

- *Break Rate*: Measures routing entries switching entirely between reachable and unreachable states. This ensures that temporary physical link outages are distinguished from ordinary algorithmic path recalculations.
- *GS Renumbering Rate*: Counts destination-address alterations directly caused by ground terminal mobility and physical handovers.

4.4. Implementation Validation Setup

We use LEOPath to validate the implementations of the three routing families over dynamic constellation evolution. Four parameterized constellation configurations adopted from Hypatia are used in this evaluation, summarized in Table 2. These four configurations (`starlink`, `oneweb`, `kuiper`, and `telesat`) span a wide range of orbit counts, per-plane populations, and total sizes, from 351 satellites (Telesat) to 1 584 (Starlink), capturing the operational diversity of currently deployed and planned broadband LEO constellations.

Beyond their scale, these are parameterized constellation designs rather than instantaneous snapshots imported from public TLE catalogs such as CelesTrak [40]. This distinction matters because averaging many snapshots from a single TLE-derived scenario would only average over time for one specific realized deployment, whose temporary gaps, uneven filling, or maintenance state may reflect that catalog epoch rather than the underlying architectural design. The goal here is to compare routing behavior at the level of the constellation design itself; therefore, idealized parameterized configurations are used to represent each architectural point, followed by temporal averaging within each run. Concretely, each configuration is propagated with SGP4-based orbital dynamics and, for the primary matrix used here, sampled every minute over a six-hour window, yielding 360 topology snapshots per run.

For each constellation, two ISL connectivity regimes are considered, corresponding to the scenarios described in Section 2.2: the *Ring* scenario (two ISLs per satellite, intra-plane only) and the *+Grid* scenario (four ISLs per satellite, combining intra-plane and inter-plane links). These two regimes expose degree-2 and degree-4 behavior in representative regular ISL designs.

The +Grid model used in this paper is intentionally a regular four-neighbor logical mesh. It captures the recurring inter-plane neighbor swap

Table 2: Constellation Configurations Used in the Evaluation

Constellation	Planes	Sats/Plane	Total Sats
Starlink	22	72	1 584
OneWeb	18	36	648
Kuiper	34	34	1 156
Telesat	27	13	351

around polar crossings, but it does not impose a polar inter-plane ISL shut-down zone or specialized seam-recovery mechanism. We do, however, evaluate removal of the counter-rotating cross-seam wrap separately, as a dedicated robustness test (Section 4.5). The results should therefore be interpreted as evidence for the regular Ring and +Grid routing families under dynamic orbital evolution—extended to a single open seam boundary—not as a claim that greedy topological forwarding is already sufficient for every operational polar-void or failure-impaired deployment variant.

Traffic endpoints are GSs. The evaluation uses 24 GSs placed at major population centers spanning all inhabited continents (e.g., New York, São Paulo, London, Lagos, Cairo, Moscow, Mumbai, Beijing, Tokyo, Sydney), as defined in the `ground_stations_dense` configuration distributed with LEOPath. Path-quality and delivery metrics are computed over all 552 ordered GS pairs at every snapshot. Each GS attaches to a single serving satellite: at every snapshot, LEOPath recomputes GSL visibility and attaches each GS to its nearest visible satellite. Consequently, attachment changes are driven purely by orbital motion. This distinction matters when interpreting route-instability later: the GS handover rate is an input induced by the attachment policy, whereas routing instability measures how strongly each algorithm reacts to that same mobility.

4.5. Evaluation Results

The evaluation separates the three routing families along four dimensions: stored forwarding state, satellite-local update burden, path quality, and packet-carried forwarding information. Table 3 presents the primary quantitative matrix across the four constellation configurations and both ISL connectivity regimes.

Data-plane footprint. Figure 11 shows the largest separation. Across the four shared constellations in the merged 1-minute +Grid matrix, link-state

Table 3: Evaluation matrix summarising the primary metrics, ISL topologies, constellations, and routing families compared in this section. Forwarding state is shown per constellation; remaining metrics are reported as algorithm-family aggregates common to all four constellations. The hop-only DRA baseline [11] (DRA’s direction-estimation phase, without its delay-enhancement phase) shares topological forwarding’s state, update rate, and packet locator, differing only in the distance metric; it therefore appears explicitly in the distance-stretch and seam-delivery rows, where its hop metric leaves physical-distance optimality unexploited. [†]Seam delivery is measured on the seam (cylinder) model, in which the physically-infeasible cross-seam inter-plane links are removed, leaving the orbital-plane dimension open: the pivot metric, built from measured ISL geometry, delivers all 552 ordered GS pairs, whereas the hop metric assumes the cyclic wrap and loops at the open boundary. Link-state and explicit-path families are not evaluated on the cylinder.

Metric	Algorithm	Topology	Starlink	Kuiper	Telesat	OneWeb
Forwarding state						
(units/sat.)	Link-state	Ring	1 584	1 156	351	648
		+Grid	1 584	1 156	351	648
	Topological	Ring	2.24	2.31	2.52	2.64
		+Grid	4.24	4.31	4.52	4.64
	Explicit-path	Ring	2.34	2.45	2.92	2.91
		+Grid	4.60	4.80	6.03	5.49
Routing table updates						
(per sat./snap)	Link-state	Ring	1.732	0.950	0.513	1.178
		+Grid	38.29	32.52	14.11	21.59
	Topological	Ring	0.025	0.029	0.048	0.036
		+Grid	0.025	0.029	0.048	0.036
	Explicit-path	Ring	0.183	0.231	0.325	0.308
		+Grid	0.625	0.747	1.187	0.938
Mean distance stretch						
(GS-pair)	Link-state	Ring	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
		+Grid	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	Topological	Ring	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
		+Grid	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
	Hop-only (δ_{hop})	Ring	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
		+Grid	1.025	1.028	1.023	1.020
	Explicit-path	Ring	1.005	1.008	1.015	1.002
		+Grid	1.002	1.002	1.002	1.002
Seam delivery						
(cylinder, % of 552)	Topological	+Grid [†]	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Hop-only (δ_{hop})	+Grid [†]	77.0	87.2	91.1	79.2
Packet-carried forwarding info						
	Link-state	Ring/+Grid	16 B	16 B	16 B	16 B
	Topological	Ring/+Grid	3 B	3 B	3 B	3 B
	Explicit-path	Ring	~129 B	~129 B	~129 B	~129 B
		+Grid	~157 B	~157 B	~157 B	~157 B

Figure 11: Default data-plane footprint in the shared +Grid comparison matrix. Values are means across Starlink, Kuiper, OneWeb, and Telesat and are plotted on logarithmic axes. Topological forwarding collapses both stored satellite-local forwarding state and routing table updates, while the $R = 3$ dynamic explicit-path algorithm remains low-state but still refreshes ingress bindings substantially more often than topological forwarding.

averages 934.75 forwarding-state units per satellite because each node stores destination-oriented state for all routable satellites. Topological forwarding averages only 4.43 units because default state is bounded by local neighbor degree. The $R = 3$ dynamic explicit-path algorithm remains close to this low-state regime at 5.23 units, since the counted satellite-local state is limited to interface entries and ingress bindings; the full trajectory is instead represented as packet-carried forwarding information.

Satellite-local maintenance. Routing table updates show an even sharper operational separation. In +Grid, link-state requires an average of 26.63 installed updates per satellite per snapshot across the four constellations (14.11–38.29, growing with constellation size), driven by repeated global shortest-path recomputation. The $R = 3$ dynamic explicit-path algorithm requires 0.874 updates on average (0.63–1.19) as ingress bindings refresh with attachment and cached-path changes. Topological forwarding requires only 0.034 updates per satellite per snapshot on average (0.025–0.048); notably, its update rate is identical in Ring and +Grid, because installed-state changes are driven solely by GS attachment events rather than by ISL topology. Thus, when measuring installed state mutations rather than path-outcome changes, topological forwarding installs roughly $780\times$ fewer updates than link-state and $25\times$ fewer than the explicit-path algorithm.

The same state-size ordering persists across the individual constellation sizes and plane configurations summarized in Table 3. Link-state forwarding state follows constellation size, topological forwarding stays tied to local ISL

degree, and the explicit-path algorithm stays close to topological forwarding in stored state but above it in update rate because ingress bindings change with attachment and path planning decisions.

Path quality and delivery. The reduction in state and update rate does not create a measurable path-quality penalty in the evaluated regular Ring/+Grid models. Table 3 shows that link-state maintains stretch 1.00 by construction and that pivot-weighted topological forwarding matches this within numerical precision, with mean and P95 distance stretch of 1.000 and a maximum observed per-run mean of 1.000001. As a sanity control, explicit-path routing at $R = 1$ also reaches mean stretch 1.000 because paths are replanned every snapshot. This is not the main explicit-path comparison point; the main comparison uses $R = 3$ dynamic reuse, where delivered-path stretch remains small at 1.002.

Because the pivot-weighted score is a heuristic refinement rather than a proven weighted-shortest-path metric (Section 3.3.2), we also report exhaustive worst-case evidence rather than only means. In the +Grid regime, all 552 ordered GS pairs produced a delivered greedy path in every one of the 360 snapshots of all four constellations—794,880 forwarding walks in total. No delivery failure, routing loop, or greedy local minimum was observed in any of them; the corresponding Ring runs add a further 56,223 delivered walks over the intra-plane-reachable pairs, with the same outcome. Hop-count stretch is exactly 1.0 in every sample, consistent with Lemma 1. For distance stretch, the worst single delivered-path sample across all runs is 1.0055 (Telesat, +Grid); the worst samples for Kuiper, OneWeb, and Starlink are 1.000022, 1.000007, and 1.000000, respectively. The pivot estimator’s optimality gap in these regular models is therefore confined to isolated samples below a 0.6% detour, rather than reflecting a systematic deviation from snapshot-shortest paths.

Figure 12 isolates the explicit-path reuse trade-off. Under strict $R = 3$, delivered +Grid stretch remains near-shortest at 1.0005, but delivery falls to 82.1% because cached egress choices become stale. Dynamic final-egress repair restores +Grid delivery to 100% and Ring delivery to 98.4%, with small stretch penalties of 1.002 and 1.007, respectively.

The pivot-weighted refinement is what separates the proposed scheme from hop-only logical-coordinate forwarding. Because the hop-only baseline (Section 4.2) shares the proposed scheme’s forwarding state, update rate, and decision locality and differs only in the distance function, the comparison

Figure 12: Explicit-path final-egress sensitivity in the shared +Grid matrix. Strict $R = 3$ loses delivery when cached egress satellites no longer see the destination ground station. Dynamic final-egress repair restores +Grid delivery while keeping the same carried core path, with a small delivered-path detour.

isolates the contribution of that function; we stress that this baseline is DRA’s direction-estimation phase, not full DRA, whose delay-enhancement phase is itself distance-aware but tailored to the idealized Walker model. Table 3 reports it. On the regular +Grid, the hop-only metric delivers all pairs but with mean distance stretch of 1.020–1.028 and worst-case samples up to 1.36, because it cannot distinguish equal-hop paths of different physical length, whereas the pivot metric holds stretch at 1.000. On the Ring topology the two coincide, since intra-plane links carry no inter-plane length asymmetry to exploit. The pivot refinement therefore removes a 2–3% mean (and up to 36% worst-case) physical detour at no cost in forwarding state.

The +Grid results above use the regular torus model, in which the orbital-plane dimension wraps from the last plane back to the first. That wrap corresponds to an inter-plane link across the constellation seam, where adjacent planes counter-rotate and a stable ISL is not physically realizable. To confirm that the proposed result does not depend on this idealization, we re-evaluate on a *seam* (cylinder) model in which the cross-seam inter-plane links are removed, leaving the plane dimension open. Concretely, the cut deletes every inter-plane ISL between the last orbital plane and plane 0—the wrap edges that close the plane cycle—turning that cycle into an open path (a cylinder). All intra-plane links and every other inter-plane link are left intact. Figure 13 illustrates the cut: a packet whose destination lies just across the removed

wrap must now detour the long way around the open plane axis, which the measured-geometry pivot metric does naturally, whereas the hop-only metric still assumes the wrap exists and loops at the open boundary. As shown in Table 3, the pivot scheme is unaffected: it delivers all 552 GS pairs at mean stretch 1.000 across all four constellations, because its distance estimator is built from the actual ISL geometry and therefore never attempts to route across a link that is absent. The hop-only metric, in contrast, assumes the cyclic wrap and loops at the seam, losing 9–23% of pairs depending on constellation. This is a direct consequence of grounding the metric in measured geometry rather than in the logical torus, and it is the same property that yields the stretch advantage above. It is also where full DRA’s analytic enhancement would not help: that rule presupposes the regular Walker grid the seam model breaks, whereas the pivot estimator depends only on the measured edge set. We emphasize the scope of this test: the seam model removes only the cross-seam wrap and does not model polar inter-plane deactivation zones or arbitrary link failures, which create interior voids and remain future work (Section 5.4).

Structural trade-off. Table 4 summarizes the architectural trade-offs that are not already visible from the detailed resource and stretch matrix in Table 3. Link-state preserves exact global shortest paths at the cost of destination-oriented state that scales with constellation size. The explicit-path algorithm avoids large backbone forwarding tables, but introduces source-side planning, non-zero packet-carried path stacks, and recurring ingress refresh activity. Topological forwarding minimizes both stored default state and satellite-side routing table updates by replacing destination-oriented routing tables with deterministic local coordinate arithmetic.

Figure 13: The seam (cylinder) cut, on the +Grid logical grid unrolled along the orbital-plane axis. The inter-plane wrap edges between the last plane and plane 0 (marked \bowtie) are removed because adjacent planes there counter-rotate and cannot sustain a stable ISL; the plane axis is therefore open rather than cyclic, while the satellite-slot axis stays closed. For a source–destination pair straddling the removed wrap, the pivot metric, built from measured ISL geometry, routes the long way around the open axis and delivers, whereas the hop-only (δ_{hop}) metric still assumes the wrap exists and loops at the open boundary.

Figure 14: Packet-carried forwarding information in the shared +Grid matrix. Link-state is shown with a 16-byte IPv6 destination address, while topological forwarding is shown with the current 23-bit 6G-RUPA topological locator rounded to 3 bytes. Explicit-path routing is shown as an SRv6 SRH-equivalent segment stack, assuming each carried segment identifier is a 128-bit IPv6 address and excluding the IPv6 base header. These byte counts are not symmetric in what they buy: the 16-byte IPv6 address provides global reachability and a globally unique endpoint identity, whereas the 3-byte locator is meaningful only within the constellation-backbone scope and presumes a separate identity namespace and name-to-locator resolution, whose signaling cost is accounted for in Section 5.1.

Table 4: Algorithm trade-off summary for the primary shared 1-minute matrix. Unlike Table 3, which reports the detailed per-constellation resource and stretch measurements, this table highlights the cross-family behavioral distinctions that are not directly visible from those raw values: effective next-hop instability, delivery under path reuse, and the primary architectural scaling pressure of each routing family. Explicit-path values use $R = 3$ dynamic final-egress repair, with strict $R = 3$ and $R = 1$ sanity-control values annotated where relevant.

Metric	Link-state	Topological	Explicit-path algorithm
Effective instability (+Grid sat→GS)	0.244	0.073	$R = 3$ dyn.: 0.060 $R = 3$ strict: 0.059 $R = 1$ sanity: 0.073
Delivery (+Grid pairs)	1.000	1.000	$R = 3$ dyn.: 1.000 $R = 3$ strict: 0.821 $R = 1$ sanity: 1.000
Default forwarding model	Global destination-based next-hop state	Local coordinate arithmetic	Ingress-computed carried path
Main scaling pressure	Per-satellite state, recomputation, and FIB churn	Edge mobility signaling and local exception state	Ingress planning, binding refresh, and packet-header growth
Main strength	Exact paths	shortest Minimal default state and updates	Flexible steering with low satellite-local state
Main trade-off	High plane maintenance	Requires topological address semantics	Header overhead and reuse/delivery sensitivity

5. Discussion

The evaluation supports a specific architectural interpretation: in the regular Ring and +Grid ISL models evaluated here, topological addressing moves the default forwarding problem from destination-oriented routing tables into local address arithmetic. Within that scope, 6G-RUPA trades global forwarding state for local computation while preserving shortest-path quality within numerical precision.

The important distinction is not simply that one algorithm has fewer table entries than another. Each routing family absorbs mobility and topology dynamics in a different place. Link-state routing keeps exact global shortest paths by maintaining destination-oriented satellite state and recomputing it as the topology evolves. Explicit-path routing reduces hop-by-hop destination tables, but moves complexity into ingress planning, cached bindings, and packet-carried path information. Topological forwarding keeps the default satellite data plane local: each satellite needs its immediate neighbor addresses and a deterministic rule for selecting the next hop. The following discussion interprets the consequences of that design choice and the boundaries of the present evidence.

5.1. Control-Plane Locality and Edge Renumbering

The routing-update metric measures installed local satellite state changes, not merely changes in the path that a packet would follow. This distinction is central to the comparison. In the shared +Grid matrix, topological forwarding reduces the mean update rate from 26.63 updates per satellite and snapshot under link-state to 0.034. The explicit-path algorithm remains low-state, but the primary $R = 3$ dynamic setting still performs 0.874 updates per satellite and snapshot on average because ingress bindings refresh as attachments and cached plans change. Thus, the topological result is not only a smaller table; it is a nearly static default satellite data plane during orbital motion.

The same update count has different operational meaning for each family. In the link-state baseline, a snapshot change can alter many destination-oriented next hops after global shortest-path recomputation. The maintenance burden is therefore global in scope even before modeling Link State Advertisement (LSA) flooding, protocol timers, or transient convergence. In topological forwarding, the default next-hop decision is algorithmic: a satellite compares the destination locator against its immediate neighbors and

chooses the best local progression. Stored state changes only when the local neighbor set or an attachment-related exception changes. The explicit-path algorithm sits between these extremes: it avoids global destination-oriented satellite tables, but still maintains ingress bindings and carries path guidance that is not counted as satellite-local table state.

Effective next-hop instability should therefore be read as a companion signal rather than as a substitute for routing updates. Instability measures route-outcome volatility, while routing updates measure installed state mutations. A topological next hop can change because a destination GS has moved to a new serving satellite, but that does not require a constellation-wide table update. Conversely, explicit-path reuse can lower observed next-hop volatility by holding a cached path across multiple snapshots, but the strict $R = 3$ sensitivity shows why this metric is insufficient on its own: cached egresses can remain stable while delivery fails after the destination GS moves out of view. Dynamic final-egress repair restores +Grid delivery with only a small delivered-path stretch penalty, but it also makes the dependence on ingress planning and repair policy explicit.

The $R = 1$ explicit-path run is best interpreted as a sanity control. It recomputes source-selected shortest paths every snapshot and therefore reaches the same mean stretch of 1.000 as the shortest-path baseline. The primary $R = 3$ dynamic case exposes the more relevant reuse trade-off: lower outcome instability than per-snapshot planning, full +Grid delivery after final-egress repair, and a small delivered-path stretch penalty.

The topological +Grid instability value of 0.073 should be interpreted as the observed shortest-path-following baseline under the evaluated topology model, attachment policy, and one-minute sampling interval. It reflects physical and geometric changes in the scenario: satellites move at approximately 28,000 km/h, shortest end-to-end paths can shift between snapshots, and GSs attach to new serving satellites. The higher link-state instability value of 0.244 is driven by a different mechanism. In a regular grid, many equal-cost shortest paths can exist, so a shortest-path implementation may flap between topologically equivalent alternatives because of tie-breaking. Topological forwarding avoids much of that effect through deterministic pivot-weighted geometry. Per-snapshot explicit planning can do the same, but only by continually recomputing and reinstalling ingress-selected paths.

Sampling-interval sensitivity. Because the maintenance and instability figures above are measured per snapshot, they could in principle be artifacts

of the one-minute sampling interval used throughout the evaluation. To rule this out, we re-ran the +Grid topological and link-state matrices at a ten-times-finer (10 s) and a five-times-coarser (5 min) interval over the same six-hour horizon, for all four constellations. Two quantities are sampling-invariant by construction and are confirmed so empirically: the per-satellite forwarding-state size is identical at every interval (topological mean degree ≈ 4.2 – 4.6 ; link-state equal to the satellite count), and delivered-path stretch is unchanged (mean 1.000 in all cases, with topological worst-case stretch ≤ 1.006). The maintenance burden does depend on the interval, but in a way that strengthens rather than weakens the headline contrast. Table 5 reports the satellite forwarding-state update rate normalized per hour, so that intervals are compared on equal footing. The topological update rate stays negligible and roughly flat across the full $30\times$ range of sampling intervals, whereas the link-state update rate is orders of magnitude larger at every interval and *grows* as sampling tightens, because each global recomputation captures finer-grained topology change. The one-minute interval is therefore conservative for the comparison: a finer interval only widens the gap in favor of topological forwarding. The per-snapshot GS handover and renumbering rates instead rise mechanically toward saturation as the interval lengthens (nearly every GS changes its serving satellite within a five-minute window), which is precisely why the update burden is reported as a per-hour rate rather than a per-snapshot count.

Table 5: Sampling-interval sensitivity of the satellite forwarding-state update rate (updates per hour, normalized across intervals) in the +Grid matrix, given as the range across the four constellations. Forwarding-state size and delivered-path stretch are sampling-invariant and omitted. The 10 s ranges cover the constellations up to Kuiper scale (topological) and OneWeb scale (link-state); the largest 10 s link-state cases were not run for compute reasons, and the trend is already monotone. Full per-constellation values are in the artifact dataset.

Sampling interval	Topological (upd/h)	Link-state (upd/h)
10 s	2.0–3.1	921–1,453
1 min	1.5–2.9	847–2,297
5 min	0.4–1.6	504–564

Renumbering also needs careful interpretation. In the evaluated Ring and +Grid models, satellites retain stable logical coordinates because their relevant relative neighborhoods remain stable in the topological address struc-

ture. Renumbering is confined to the ground segment: a GS receives a locator associated with its current serving satellite and changes that locator when handover changes the attachment point. The GS renumbering rate is therefore reported separately from routing updates because it tracks edge mobility events, not repeated satellite-side readdressing.

This separation matters for overhead accounting. Let M denote the active ground-terminal population, T_{ho} the mean handover interval, and L_{sig} the mean size of one location-update transaction. The aggregate signaling rate required to maintain the ground-segment location mapping is then

$$\lambda_{sig} = \frac{M}{T_{ho}}, \quad B_{sig} = \lambda_{sig} L_{sig}.$$

As a worked example, if $M = 10^6$ active terminals, $T_{ho} = 300$ s, and $L_{sig} = 150$ bytes, then $\lambda_{sig} \approx 3,333$ updates/s and $B_{sig} \approx 500$ KB/s. This load scales linearly with the active population and with the inverse of the handover interval. It is therefore a ground-segment mobility-management cost, not a satellite-side routing-table scaling cost. A GS handover already requires signaling to update attachment state and maintain service continuity; assigning a new topological GS locator belongs to that same edge-local workflow. The control-plane contrast is therefore not “renumbering versus no renumbering,” but “edge-localized handover-driven maintenance” versus “network-wide dissemination and repeated per-node shortest-path/FIB re-computation.”

An honest accounting must also name what this edge-local workflow does not yet solve: the correspondent side of a renumbering event. When a GS acquires a new locator, peers holding the old locator must learn the new one, which is the classical rendezvous problem of locator-identifier architectures such as LISP and ILNP [35, 36]. Between the handover and that resolution there is a stale-locator window in which in-flight packets still target the previous serving satellite; mitigations include short-lived forwarding state at the old attachment point or resolution through the scope’s name-to-locator mapping, but the present simulator models neither correspondent-side resolution nor in-flight packet fate. The L_{sig} term above accounts for one location-update transaction per handover; characterizing the stale-window behavior and the mapping-system load under realistic traffic remains future work.

This also illustrates why identity-location separation matters. In traditional TCP/IP architectures, an address often acts both as a stable endpoint identifier and as a topological locator. In a LEO access environment, those

roles are in tension: locator changes are normal because serving satellites change frequently, while transport and application sessions expect stable end-point identity. 6G-RUPA separates these roles by binding flows to location-independent names while using topological locators as temporary forwarding synonyms. The present simulator validates the routing and renumbering behavior needed by that design, but it does not model transport sessions directly; end-to-end session-continuity validation remains future work.

5.2. Data-Plane Overhead and Packet Headers

The data-plane implication follows from both state size and lookup work. Destination-oriented forwarding in large routers commonly relies on TCAM or similarly costly associative lookup structures, and prior work shows that lookup energy scales with table size [4, 21]. Topological forwarding replaces hundreds to thousands of destination entries with a bounded local neighbor set and a small number of integer comparisons over address tuples. We do not measure spacecraft power directly, so the energy argument remains an inference from measured forwarding-state reduction and established lookup-cost literature. The measured result nevertheless points to a concrete engineering pressure point for LEO: reducing the default lookup work performed by every satellite on every forwarding decision.

For completeness we note the per-decision compute cost. The pivot-weighted score is a minimum over S precomputed inter- and intra-plane path costs per neighbor, i.e. $O(kS)$ floating-point add-and-compare operations per forwarding decision; the deterministic geometry costs d_{intra} and d_{inter} are precomputed once per snapshot, and per-destination results are cacheable. For the evaluated constellations ($k \leq 4$, $S \leq 72$) this amounts to at most a few hundred elementary operations over a small precomputed table, with no runtime orbital-geometry computation, and is therefore inexpensive relative to a power-hungry associative lookup. We nonetheless frame the energy argument as a memory- and lookup-side claim rather than a measured total-energy result, since net on-board power depends on router-implementation details we do not measure.

Packet-carried forwarding information is a separate data-plane dimension. Link-state forwarding can operate with a conventional destination locator; under an IPv6 data plane this is a 16-byte destination address. A simulator-only satellite or GS identifier could be smaller, but an IP-style deployment would normally carry an IP destination address. Topological forwarding also needs a destination locator, but 6G-RUPA allows that locator to be scoped

to the constellation. In the evaluated backbone locator, the current tuple allocates 4 bits for shell, 7 bits for orbital plane, 7 bits for satellite position, and 5 bits for the local endpoint index, for a total of 23 bits, rounded to 3 bytes when serialized. Larger endpoint spaces would require more endpoint bits or an indirection mechanism. This comparison should be read with its scope in mind: the 16-byte IPv6 address buys global reachability and a globally unique endpoint identity, whereas the 3-byte 6G-RUPA locator is meaningful only within the constellation-backbone scope and presumes a separate identity namespace and name-to-locator resolution, whose signaling cost is accounted for in the edge-mobility discussion of Section 5.1. The byte counts therefore compare per-packet forwarding overhead inside the backbone scope, not the total architectural cost of reaching an arbitrary Internet endpoint.

Explicit-path families carry more than a destination locator: they carry path information in packet metadata. This reduces dependence on large hop-by-hop destination tables, but introduces overhead that grows with the number of carried segments, checkpoints, or forwarding identifiers. As summarized in Figure 14, the evaluated explicit-path segment stack maps to 129.3 B of SRv6 SRH-equivalent carried information in Ring and 156.7 B in +Grid, computed as $8 + 16k$ bytes for k carried segment identifiers and excluding the IPv6 base header. This assumes the usual SRv6 representation in which each segment identifier is a 128-bit IPv6 address. Changing the refresh interval changes when the path stack is replanned; it does not remove the non-zero path metadata carried by explicit-path forwarding. The simulator also tracks a compact internal path-identifier representation, but that representation is not a deployed wire-format claim and is therefore not used as the main packet-overhead comparison point.

For SRv6 or SR-MPLS, the main comparison point is not that explicit-path routing is simply better or worse. It targets traffic steering and policy control. In such systems, the network still maintains reachability toward segment or checkpoint endpoints, while ingress nodes compute and store policies. In the IPv6 case, packet overhead depends on forwarding mode. The SRH itself adds $8 + 16k$ bytes for a stack of k segments, excluding the IPv6 base header [41]. For inline SRv6, this overhead is

$$H_{\text{inline}} = 8 + 16k,$$

whereas for encapsulation mode an additional 40-byte outer IPv6 header is

required,

$$H_{\text{encap}} = 40 + 8 + 16k.$$

Under a 1280-byte or 1500-byte maximum transmission unit (MTU), payload efficiency decreases linearly with k . We intentionally treat this relationship parametrically rather than assuming a specific segment depth for LEO deployments. If the resulting packet exceeds the path MTU, IPv6 routers cannot fragment it in flight; the source must reduce payload or fragment at the source [42, 41].

This is also where the broader 6G-RUPA architecture becomes relevant. Unlike Internet Protocol version 4 (IPv4)/IPv6, which impose fixed address widths, 6G-RUPA allows address formats to be tailored to the scope and topology being served. If packet-carried path information is desired for selected traffic classes, the identifiers used in that header need not be 128-bit addresses. In principle, a constellation-backbone scope could encode shorter path labels or topological locators while preserving the semantics needed inside that scope. This does not remove the explicit-path trade-off, but it means that header overhead can be reduced in a scope-specific architecture rather than being locked to conventional IP address sizes.

5.3. Paradigm Comparison: Where 6G-RUPA Fits

The broader LEO routing design space can be organized into four families. *Link-state routing* disseminates global topology information and installs destination-oriented forwarding state. *Explicit-path routing* carries path information in the packet and includes SRv6/SR-MPLS, geographic checkpoint routing, and LiR. *Hierarchical stabilization* reduces instability and state through partitioning or domains, as in BlockFLEX and SHORT. *Topological forwarding*, which is the focus of this work, derives default forwarding directly from node location encoded in the address.

The purpose of this comparison is not to claim a universally superior design. These families optimize different objectives. Link-state routing prioritizes exact global shortest paths and familiar control semantics. Explicit-path schemes prioritize steering and policy expression. Hierarchical schemes prioritize instability containment. 6G-RUPA targets a different default operating point: minimal satellite-local state and minimal default routing table updates, with richer policies added where needed. Table 6 summarizes that distinction using architectural wording rather than scenario-specific asymptotic claims.

Table 6: Architectural comparison with representative routing families for LEO constellations.

Paradigm	FIB State	Signaling	Packet Overhead	Voiding	Handling	Traffic Engineering
OSPF/IS-IS	Destination-oriented, grows with routable nodes	High global flooding and recomputation	None in packet	None in principle; globally computed paths		High
GCR [43]	Reduced core hop-by-hop state; policies concentrated at ingress / edges	Low to moderate; tied to policy updates rather than full flooding	Non-zero checkpoint / segment guidance	Low; checkpoints can steer around voids		High
LiR [44]	Reduced forwarding-table dependence	Low to moderate; rerouting handled through packet identifiers and local repair	Non-zero Bloom-filter forwarding identifiers	Low; source-selected paths avoid pure greedy trapping, with probabilistic trade-offs		Medium
BlockFLEX [45] / SHORT [2]	Hierarchically bounded intra-block / intra-domain state	Low to moderate; instability localized inside partitions	Low to none in normal forwarding	Low; hierarchy masks seam volatility		High
Orthodromic [46]	Bounded entries, geometry-derived	Low to moderate; link-state-assisted recovery	None in packet	Low; hybrid escapes holes and local minima		Medium to high
6G-RUPA (Ours)	Constant local state proportional to node degree	No global default-path dissemination; ground mobility handled by edge signaling	No extra path-stack metadata	Exception policies for edge cases		Low default; extendable via policies

The comparison also clarifies the scope of the present simulator evidence. In the current LEOPath artifact set, the explicit-path algorithm is a family-level abstraction rather than a protocol-faithful SRv6, GCR, or LiR implementation. The architectural comparison is therefore broader than the protocol fidelity reached by the simulator. The overhead distinction remains important: topological and link-state forwarding carry only a destination locator in the default case, whereas deployed explicit-path schemes introduce non-zero path-stack or checkpoint overhead whenever path information is carried in the packet.

LiR contrasts with deterministic topological forwarding by moving path information into packet-carried Bloom filters, which reduces forwarding-table dependence but introduces probabilistic false-positive trade-offs [44]. GCR reduces full hop-by-hop state by steering packets through geographic checkpoints, but still relies on explicit packet-carried path information and ingress-side path selection rather than purely local default forwarding [43]. Relative to these approaches, 6G-RUPA targets a lower-overhead default data plane: no per-packet segment stack for GCR-like routing and no Bloom-filter-based probabilistic forwarding for LiR-like routing.

A closely related recent design point is orthodromic routing [46], which, like the present scheme, keeps a bounded number of forwarding-table entries by deriving forwarding from constellation geometry. It differs in two ways relevant here. First, it is an explicit hybrid that augments greedy geographic decisions with link-state-derived awareness specifically to escape the topology holes and greedy local minima that pure geographic forwarding cannot resolve—precisely the interior-void case we treat as future work (Section 5.4)—whereas our default rule is purely local and delegates void handling to optional EFCP exception policies. Second, it is formulated as a standalone constellation protocol, while our contribution realizes low-state topological forwarding as a scope-specific policy of a recursive user plane shared with the terrestrial segment. Lightweight segment-routing designs that bound state through landmark-based skeleton graphs [47] sit on the explicit-path side of this space, trading a compact carried path for reduced per-node tables. Relative to both, 6G-RUPA targets the lowest default footprint—no carried path stack and no link-state database—at the cost of requiring explicit policies for the irregular cases those schemes handle natively.

Hierarchical approaches such as BlockFLEX and SHORT target another objective: masking or localizing LEO instability through routing domains, blocks, or overlays [45, 2]. That objective is complementary rather than

contradictory. We do not claim to supersede those schemes; instead, the evaluated design occupies a different point in the design space, where default forwarding stays simple and low-state while richer policy remains an optional overlay.

5.4. *Limitations and Threats to Validity*

Several caveats qualify these results:

- **Simulator abstraction:** The study validates forwarding state, routing table updates, route instability, delivery, and path quality under dynamic orbital evolution, but it does not model queueing delay, jitter, buffer occupancy, packet loss, congestion control, transport throughput, or end-to-end session continuity.
- **Link-state baseline:** The baseline uses all-pairs shortest-path computation as a link-state family abstraction. This captures exact shortest-path forwarding state and recomputation behavior, but it does not model deployed OSPF/IS-IS details such as LSA flooding, timer tuning, incremental computation, or transient convergence.
- **Explicit-path abstraction:** The explicit-path algorithm is a family-level model rather than a protocol-faithful segment-routing, GCR, or LiR implementation. It abstracts ingress-controller behavior, complete packet formats, repair semantics, and policy configuration. Its value here is comparative family coverage, not wire-protocol evidence for any single explicit-path protocol.
- **Regular-grid and seam assumptions:** The topological shortest-path result relies on the regular Ring/+Grid product structure and the corresponding pivot-weighted discrete-torus distance. The seam-robustness result of Section 4.5 extends this to a cylinder model in which the cross-seam inter-plane wrap is removed, and shows that the pivot metric tolerates that specific irregularity where the hop-based metric does not. This should not, however, be read as general void resilience: we do not model polar inter-plane shutdown regions or arbitrary failure patterns, which create interior voids rather than a single open boundary and can trap greedy forwarding at a local minimum. Such cases would require additional exception policies or a different EFCP forwarding policy, and a seam-aware metric whose tie-break and

progress rules are made open-axis throughout; we leave the full treatment to future work.

- **Packet-overhead model:** The explicit-path overhead comparison uses an SRv6 SRH-equivalent encoding to provide a concrete wire-format reference. Other encodings, compression mechanisms, or scope-specific identifiers could reduce absolute byte counts, but would not remove the design distinction between destination-locator forwarding and packet-carried path metadata.
- **No traffic or load model:** The evaluation is geometric and topological; it does not model offered traffic, link utilization, queueing, or load distribution. Greedy single-path topological forwarding performs no load balancing and can concentrate traffic on the high-latitude inter-plane crossings that the pivot metric favors. Multipath/Equal-Cost Multi-Path (ECMP)-style spreading and congestion-aware steering are out of scope here and left to future work.
- **Energy inference:** The energy argument is inferred from measured state reduction plus prior TCAM lookup literature, not from direct spacecraft-power measurement.

Longer horizons, richer traffic matrices, seam-deactivated scenarios, hardware power measurements, transport-layer validation, and heterogeneous multi-shell topologies remain open extensions.

5.5. Broader Architectural Vision

This paper studies one 6G-RUPA capability in depth: topological addressing and low-state forwarding inside the constellation backbone scope. The broader architecture allows scope-specific policies across access, backbone, and inter-constellation segments; separates stable identities from temporary forwarding locators; and permits address structures sized for the topology being served. The evaluation validates one concrete instantiation of those principles. Multi-layer routing, multi-constellation operation, hybrid satellite-terrestrial policy composition, and direct validation of session-continuity mechanisms remain future work.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

The deployment of LEO mega-constellations presents both an opportunity and a challenge for global communications. While these networks promise ubiquitous connectivity, they expose the fundamental limitations of routing protocols designed for static terrestrial topologies. The resulting scalability and energy constraints—driven by thousands of satellites, continuous topology change, and strict on-board power budgets—demand a new architectural approach.

This paper has demonstrated that such an approach is feasible and effective within the evaluated simulator scope. By encoding each satellite’s logical position within the constellation directly into its network address, topological forwarding replaces resource-intensive global-state protocols with low-state, greedy forwarding that requires only local neighbor information. Using our purpose-built LEOPath simulation framework, we evaluated this scheme across four constellation designs under two well-known ISL topologies, with a shared comparison matrix spanning link-state, topological, and explicit-path families. Within the regular Ring and +Grid models evaluated here, topological forwarding offers the most favorable operating point across the reported metrics: it uses the smallest forwarding state, requires the fewest routing updates, preserves shortest-path quality, carries no explicit path information in packets, and exhibited no routing failures across more than 850,000 delivered forwarding walks. These results are scoped to regular topologies; seam-deactivated and failure-impaired variants remain to be evaluated with explicit exception policies. Dynamic explicit-path forwarding can recover delivery in more constrained cases, but it does so by moving complexity to ingress planning, update churn, and packet-carried path information. Link-state forwarding remains the familiar baseline, but its global-state maintenance cost makes it the least scalable option for dense, continuously moving LEO backbones.

Beyond the specific routing results, this work validates the architectural principles of 6G-RUPA: the flexibility to define scope-specific addressing policies, the separation of identity from location, and the ability to tailor protocol behavior to the physical characteristics of each network segment. The topological addressing scheme evaluated here is one concrete instantiation of these principles, applied to the constellation backbone. If future constellations adopt different regularities, seams, hierarchy, or inter-shell structures, new topological routing algorithms could be introduced as EFCP policies rather

than as fixed network-wide protocol replacements. The same mechanism could also express explicit-path or link-state behavior when those policies are appropriate for a given scope, traffic class, or operator domain. We also view the public release of LEOPath itself as a contribution: it provides an open, reusable basis for future community evaluation of routing and traffic-management ideas under realistic constellation dynamics.

The evaluation data supporting the figures and summary statistics presented in this paper is openly available in a public companion repository [48]⁸.

Several directions remain for future work. First, extending the pivot-weighted distance and exception policies to seam-deactivated, polar-void, failure-impaired, or otherwise irregular topologies. Second, validating the energy savings with hardware-in-the-loop TCAM power measurements. Third, studying mobility in greater depth, including handover, renumbering, and session continuity across moving attachment points. Fourth, extending the evaluation to inter-networking between orbital shells, satellite operators, and terrestrial ground operators, so that 6G-RUPA can be assessed as a true network-of-networks architecture rather than a single-constellation routing scheme. Finally, integrating these mechanisms with existing 3GPP control-plane procedures to demonstrate operational compatibility in realistic deployments.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Claude (Anthropic) to assist with language editing. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

⁸<https://github.com/PhD-Sergio/data-ntn-topological-evaluation>

References

- [1] C. L. Rachfal, Low earth orbit satellites: Potential to address the broadband digital divide, Tech. Rep. R46896, Congressional Research Service (2021).
URL <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/R/R46896>
- [2] Y. Li, L. Liu, H. Li, W. Liu, Y. Chen, W. Zhao, J. Wu, Q. Wu, J. Liu, Z. Lai, Stable hierarchical routing for operational leo networks, in: Proceedings of the 30th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking, ACM MobiCom '24, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2024, p. 296–311. doi:10.1145/3636534.3649362.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3636534.3649362>
- [3] M. Al-Khalidi, R. Al-Zaidi, M. Hammoudeh, Network mobility management challenges, directions, and solutions: An architectural perspective, *Electronics* 11 (17) (2022). doi:10.3390/electronics11172696.
URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/11/17/2696>
- [4] V. Ravikumar, R. Mahapatra, Tcam architecture for ip lookup using prefix properties, *IEEE Micro* 24 (2) (2004) 60–69. doi:10.1109/MM.2004.1289292.
- [5] Y. Sun, H. Liu, M. S. Kim, Using tcam efficiently for ip route lookup, in: 2011 IEEE Consumer Communications and Networking Conference (CCNC), 2011, pp. 816–817. doi:10.1109/CCNC.2011.5766609.
- [6] Thales Alenia Space (France), Ericsson (Sweden), Ericsson (France), Qualcomm France, SES Techcom, Thales - SIX, Telit Cinterion, GreenerWave, Martel Innovate, Digital for Planet, Centre Tecnologic De Telecomunicacions De Catalunya, German Aerospace Center, University of Bologna, Vision on non-terrestrial networks in 6g system (or imt-2030), in: ETSI Conference on "Non-Terrestrial Networks, a Native Component of 6G", Zenodo, Sophia Antipolis, France, 2024. doi:10.5281/zenodo.14007174.
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14007174>
- [7] Hexa-X-II Consortium, Deliverable d1.2: 6g use cases and requirements, Tech. rep., Hexa-X-II (jan 2024).

- URL https://hexa-x-ii.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Hexa-X-II_D1.2.pdf
- [8] S. Giménez-Antón, E. Grasa, J. Perelló, A. Cárdenas, 6g-rupa: A flexible, scalable, and energy-efficient user plane architecture for next-generation mobile networks, *Computers* 13 (8) (2024). doi:10.3390/computers13080186.
URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-431X/13/8/186>
- [9] ETSI, Next Generation Protocols (NGP); An example of a non-IP network protocol architecture based on RINA design principles, Tech. Rep. GR NGP 009 V1.1.1, ETSI (feb 2019).
URL https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/NGP/001_099/009/01.01.01_60/gr_ngp009v010101p.pdf
- [10] S. Giménez-Antón, E. Grasa, J. Day, M. Rizinski, L. Chitkushev, J. Perelló, Beyond 5g architectural constraints: Designing scalable-by-design user planes for mobile networks via 6g-rupa, *IEEE Access* Preprint (2026).
URL <https://hdl.handle.net/2072/489603>
- [11] E. Ekici, I. F. Akyildiz, M. D. Bender, A distributed routing algorithm for datagram traffic in LEO satellite networks, *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking* 9 (2) (2001) 137–147. doi:10.1109/90.917071.
- [12] T. R. Henderson, R. H. Katz, On distributed, geographic-based packet routing for LEO satellite networks, in: *Proceedings of IEEE GLOBECOM 2000*, Vol. 2, 2000, pp. 1119–1123. doi:10.1109/GLOCOM.2000.891311.
- [13] M. Werner, A dynamic routing concept for ATM-based satellite personal communication networks, *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* 15 (8) (1997) 1636–1648. doi:10.1109/49.634801.
- [14] R. Mauger, C. Rosenberg, QoS guarantees for multimedia services on a TDMA-based satellite network, *IEEE Communications Magazine* 35 (7) (1997) 56–65. doi:10.1109/35.601744.
- [15] S. Giménez-Antón, E. Grasa, LEOPath: An open-source LEO satellite routing simulator, *Software*, Zenodo, version 0.1.3. Source

code: <https://github.com/Fundacio-i2CAT/LEOPath> (2026).
doi:10.5281/zenodo.20744448.
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20744448>

- [16] S. Cakaj, The ground segment of the low earth orbit satellite communication, *Frontiers in Communications and Networks* 2, analyzes LEO satellite visibility durations; reports 5–15 min communication windows for typical LEO orbits, with shorter durations at higher minimum elevation angles. (2021). doi:10.3389/frcmn.2021.643095.
- [17] Y. Yang, M. Xu, D. Wang, Y. Wang, Towards energy-efficient routing in satellite networks, *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* 34 (12) (2016) 3869–3886. doi:10.1109/JSAC.2016.2611860.
- [18] R. Panigrahy, S. Sharma, Reducing tcam power consumption and increasing throughput, in: *Proceedings 10th Symposium on High Performance Interconnects*, 2002, pp. 107–112. doi:10.1109/CONNECT.2002.1039265.
- [19] K. Proffitt, Space batteries: How SpaceX designs batteries for satellites, *Battery Power Online*Detailed coverage of SpaceX principal engineer Ray Barsa’s presentation at the 2025 International Battery Seminar on LEO battery performance. (jun 2025).
- [20] TRW Defense and Space Systems Group, Space power distribution system technology. Volume 1: Reference EPS Design, Tech. Rep. NASA-CR-170852, National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), prepared for George C. Marshall Space Flight Center. Discusses foundational LEO energy storage sizing, eclipse discharge rates, and Depth of Discharge (DOD) optimization. (mar 1983).
- [21] W. Lu, S. Sahni, Low-Power TCAMs for Very Large Forwarding Tables , *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking* 18 (03) (2010) 948–959. doi:10.1109/TNET.2009.2034143.
URL <https://doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/TNET.2009.2034143>
- [22] M. Handley, Delay is not an option: Low latency routing in space, in: *Proceedings of the 17th ACM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks, HotNets ’18*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY,

- USA, 2018, p. 85–91. doi:10.1145/3286062.3286075.
URL <https://doi-org.recursos.biblioteca.upc.edu/10.1145/3286062.3286075>
- [23] H. Zhang, Y. Wang, G. Spreemann, L. R. Cenkeramaddi, M. Jonaitis, Resource allocation for semantic communication via model-driven deep learning (2024). arXiv:2406.05078.
- [24] H. Wang, H. Zhang, J. Li, S. Nao, L. R. Cenkeramaddi, M. Jonaitis, A tutorial on end-to-end learning for joint communication and sensing in 6g (2024). arXiv:2402.08988.
- [25] 3GPP, Solutions for NR to support Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), TR 38.821 V16.2.0, 3GPP, release 16 (mar 2021).
URL <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3525>
- [26] 3GPP, NR; NR and NG-RAN Overall Description; Stage 2, TS 38.300 V19.2.0, 3GPP, release 19 (Section 16.14: NTN) (dec 2024).
URL <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3191>
- [27] 3GPP, NG-RAN; Xn Application Protocol (XnAP), TS 38.423 V19.1.0, 3GPP, release 19 (dec 2024).
URL <https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/Specifications/SpecificationDetails.aspx?specificationId=3228>
- [28] 3GPP, Study on security aspects of satellite access (Release 18), Technical Report (TR) 33.700-28, 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), version 18.0.0 (06 2023).
- [29] 3GPP, Study on Management Aspects of NTN Phase 2 (Release 19), Technical Report (TR) 28.874, 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), version 19.1.0 (03 2025).
- [30] J. Garcia-Cabeza, J. Albert-Smet, Z. Frias, L. Mendo, S. A. Azcoitia, E. Yraola, Direct-to-cell: A first look into starlink’s direct satellite-to-device radio access network through crowdsourced measurements, *IEEE Communications Magazine* Also available as arXiv:2506.00283 (2025). doi:10.1109/MCOM.001.2500350.

- [31] X. Cao, Y. Li, X. Xiong, J. Wang, Dynamic routings in satellite networks: An overview, *Sensors* 22 (12) (2022). doi:10.3390/s22124552.
URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/12/4552>
- [32] J. Saltzer, On the naming and binding of network destinations, RFC 1498, Internet Engineering Task Force (aug 1993). doi:10.17487/RFC1498.
URL <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc1498>
- [33] C. Li, G.-Y. Li, J.-G. Wang, Requirements and gap analysis for addressing in information-centric satellite-terrestrial integrated network, Internet-Draft draft-li-istn-addressing-requirement-05, Internet Engineering Task Force, work in Progress (jul 2024).
URL <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-li-istn-addressing-requirement-05>
- [34] Z. Ding, H. Liu, F. Tian, Z. Yang, N. Wang, Fast-convergence reinforcement learning for routing in leo satellite networks, *Sensors* 23 (11) (2023). doi:10.3390/s23115180.
URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/11/5180>
- [35] D. Farinacci, V. Fuller, D. Meyer, D. Lewis, The locator/id separation protocol (LISP), RFC 6830 (Jan. 2013). doi:10.17487/RFC6830.
URL <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc6830>
- [36] R. Atkinson, S. Bhatti, Identifier-locator network protocol (ILNP) architectural description, RFC 6740 (Nov. 2012). doi:10.17487/RFC6740.
URL <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc6740>
- [37] S. Kassing, D. Bhattacharjee, A. B. Águas, J. E. Saethre, A. Singla, Exploring the "internet from space" with hypatia, in: *Proceedings of the ACM Internet Measurement Conference, IMC '20*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2020, p. 214–229. doi:10.1145/3419394.3423635.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3419394.3423635>
- [38] S. Kassing, D. Bhattacharjee, A. B. Águas, J. E. Saethre, A. Singla, Hypatia: LEO satellite network simulation framework, *Software, software companion to the Hypatia simulation framework* (2020).
URL <https://github.com/snkas/hypatia>

- [39] M. Mosahebfard, A. Cárdenas, S. Giménez-Antón, L. Tomaszewski, Unified framework for dynamic traffic management in integrated 6g terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society* 6 (2025) 9840–9861. doi:10.1109/OJCOMS.2025.3636012.
- [40] CelesTrak, Current gp element sets, accessed: 2026-05-07 (2026). URL <https://celestrak.org/NORAD/elements/>
- [41] C. Filsfil, D. Dukes, S. Previdi, J. Leddy, S. Matsushima, D. Voyer, IPv6 Segment Routing Header (SRH), RFC 8754 (mar 2020). doi:10.17487/RFC8754. URL <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc8754>
- [42] D. S. E. Deering, B. Hinden, Internet Protocol, Version 6 (IPv6) Specification, RFC 8200 (jul 2017). doi:10.17487/RFC8200. URL <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc8200>
- [43] V. Hartig, M. Bosk, N. Mohan, P. Mendes, Segment routing based on geographic checkpoints, in: *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on LEO Networking and Communication*, 2024.
- [44] H. Zhang, Z. Wang, S. Zhang, Q. Meng, H. Luo, Link-identified routing architecture in space, *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering* (2025).
- [45] X. Wang, Blockflex: An adaptive and survivable architecture with hierarchical routing for leo satellite networks, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.17068* (2025).
- [46] P. Ashwood-Smith, B. McCormick, Orthodromic routing and forwarding for large satellite constellations (2025). *arXiv:2504.02099*. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.02099>
- [47] M. Hu, C. Wang, B. Cao, B. Zhou, Y. Dong, K. Peng, A lightweight and scalable design of segment routing in broadband LEO constellations using landmark-based skeleton graphs (2024). *arXiv:2411.19679*. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.19679>
- [48] S. Giménez-Antón, E. Grasa, J. Perelló, M. Rizinski, M. Mosahebfard, J. Day, L. Chitkushev, NTN LEO satellite routing

evaluation data, Dataset, Zenodo, version 1.0.0. Source: <https://github.com/PhD-Sergio/data-ntn-topological-evaluation>
(2026). doi:10.5281/zenodo.20744446.
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20744446>